

FORWARD

(GA 824550)

Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

WP4 - Capacity building and training activities

Guidelines for WP4

Report on Deliverable 4.1 - Capacity Building Plan

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INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION

The WP4 is the fourth Work package of FORWARD project and it is focused on Capacity building and training activities. This stage of the project is built upon the diagnostic and mapping results (WP2) of the OR's R&I Ecosystems. A detailed analysis of the current situation highlighted the importance of empowering knowledge and improve performance in order for OR's to successfully engage in challenges and opportunities of the EU financing programs.

The capacity-building plan has it start with the deliverable 4.1 Capacity building plan (M18), as the objective is to deliver a "Capacity Building Plan to define the capacity building actions to be implemented under WP4 will be drafted". This Delivery should provide the bases to develop the activities of training and capacitation within Forward project with the goal to empower human resources and to strengthen the regional R&I ecosystems in order to improve performance, increase participation and use of their excellence, more efficiently. According to the GA, the WP4 - *Capacity building and training activities* follows the WP2, as a process of "updating the regional diagnostics of the research and innovation regional ecosystems in the focus of regional RIS3 strategies, and of the specific needs of research and innovation actors in each OR for an enhanced participation in H2020, and future research programmes"

This Capacity Building plan arises as a response to the needs identified, to help stimulating and reinforcing capabilities of ORs' R&I actors through dedicated activities, co-designed by the regions, such as trainings, online courses, workshops, seminars, etc., creating a network of dedicated Regional Contact Points supporting ORs' research organizations in participating in Framework Programmes (FP).

Having the FORWARD GA as a reference point, the WP4 process can highlight three main actions according to the target actors:

a - **Capacity building activities targeting R&I actors** will be implemented with the aim of improving their competences in the European programs and fostering their international outreach. Tailored activities will be organized in each partner region, including i) trainings, workshops on EU project development and management; ii) organization of exchange knowledge and cooperation activities such as seminars/webinars/online courses/summer school activities; and iii) the promotion or reinforcement of project management offices in research institutions;

b - **Capacity building actions for ORs' Officers** will be put in place through mutual learning and twinning actions, especially with a view to support the rapid and efficient involvement of the ORs that are less used to H2020 projects;

c – **Establishment of a network of dedicated ORs’ R&I Offices** acting as regional contact points to provide support to research and innovation actors interested in participating in research framework programs.

In order to attain the previews goals, **the following actions are foreseen in WP4:**

1. **Design and implement a tailored Capacity Building Plan**, including activities targeting the main R&I actors, namely individual researchers, research organizations and companies;
2. Capacity building activities will aim not only at **increasing researchers’ skills for their participation in EU research projects** but also at **facilitating collaboration and partnerships within and among research and innovation actors in the ORs**;
3. Provide **training to Spreading Research excellence and supporting the scientific production** of a singular and **high impact research at European and International level**;
4. Provide the conditions for a **network of dedicated OR R&I Officers** to promote and support on the long term the **participation of ORs in EU Research Framework Programs**;
5. Equip the ORs with structuring **common and strategic tools** to ensure their capacities to seize opportunities.

The design of a Common Capacity Plan should take into account a multilevel & cross-sectorial approach that should privilege **innovation** at a technological & scientific level, from the mindset change and awareness, to the development and application of skills. Also the **access to financing programs**; granting the tools that will improve the knowledge, access and performance regarding finance opportunities; **International outreach**, reinforcing the network to gain new perceptive regarding new opportunities and providing the needed leverage in a competitive environment. The Capacity building plan implementation has as a goal the empowerment of the OR’s turning the challenging conditions as outermost regions into specific advantages.

In the context of the WP it’s foreseen the following outcomes:

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	Type	Dissemination level	Due date
D4.1	Capacity building plan	Report	Public	M18
D4.2	Common training programme for OR’s R&I actors	Report	Public	M18
D4.3	Common training programme for OR’s R&I officers	Report	Public	M25

D4.4	OR R&I Offices Operational and Sustainability Strategic for implementation	Report	Public	M36
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Table1 – Deliverables WP4

TARGET & ACTIVITIES

TARGET & ACTIVITIES

The WP4 plan is built based on the needs for capacities of the R&I actors towards the present framework of the European R&I in the context of the H2020 - FP8, and future FP9, Horizon Europe and other financing Programs. The information mapped by each OR under the WP2 is therefore essential to identify the transversal needs regarding the OR's capacity building plan construction.

By analyzing the present needs and opportunities, as well as the arising opportunities, adjusted to the differentiated characteristics of the OR's R&I Ecosystems (diagnosed by WP2), we propose a plan that can be adjusted to all OR's and that can fulfill the existing gap that limits the OR's to fully use the available financing opportunities. The target public for the WP4 activities are the actors of the quadruple helix of the R&I ecosystem in the OR's: public, private; academic/researcher; society.

WP4 interaction with other WP'S

The plan of activities is designed **to reinforce R&I capacities** and give a new and/or improved tools, namely on: developing proposals, proposal management; promote transfer of scientific excellence and other tools. In this last point, the networks will play a major role, being essentials to align the WP4 plan to the development of other WP, as the WP5 (network activities) or the WP3 (thematic action plans), as stated in the GA and illustrated in the image below on Figure 1.

Figure 1. Interaction between WP's. Source: FORWARD GA

In the implementations of actions of the WP4 are essential to coordinate and define common and shared tasks along FORWARD implementation. Although we can find several intercession between WP4 and other WP in FORWARD project, there are workpackages that have to work more closely with WP4 in order to fulfil and empower its impact and outcomes in the R&I ecosystem. The following image illustrates, at the light of WP4 the contributions from the other FW Workpackages.

To coordinate concrete future actions and design of a coherent route map, individual online meeting will be arranged between the WP5, WP6 and WP8 leaders. A meeting with the WP5 meeting already happened in on the 13th of March, on this regard.

Figure 2. Interaction on FORWARD of the WP4 with the other WP's of the project

Description of the main synergies with other Work Packages

WP2 - Diagnostics of ORs' R&I ecosystems

The WP2 is led by NEXA (Reunion) and it's the WP4 Capacity actions starting point, as the information's regarding the diagnose and mapping results from WP2 work, obtain trough the regional analysis made by the FORWARD partners of their R&I Ecosystems, as well as the strategy for FORWARD project (D2.5), the backbone orientation for the FORWARD WP's.

The WP2 was the base of the construction of the WP4, since it enabled the definition of who are our R&I key actors, as well as the need, namely the capacities that we need to build, as well as the common joint strategy that gave the platform from which we should design the different work packages taking in to consideration a common roadmap for the project.

WP3 – Co-creation and implementation of thematic action plans (M6-M36)

This WP3 lead by ITC (Canary Islands) and Synergile (Guadalupe) is dedicated to thematic working groups and will gather expert groups from OR's, nationally and internationally. These groups will be interconnected with WP4 due to its promotion of the international outreach and also the empowerment of the transversal capacities of the stakeholders that are part of the thematic working groups.

The WP3 benchmarking initiatives previewed in Task 3.3 (sustainability of the thematic groups) will be conducted within the WP4 initiatives foreseen in the FORWARD GA, therefore this WP should be aligned in terms of interest and goals with the WP4 initiatives, at a regional level, through the Regional Coordinator, with WP4 monitoring and follow up, aligned with WP3 leader.

WP5 – Networking actions (M15-M36)

This WP lead by GOBCAN (Canary Island) is connected with WP4 particularly through Tasks 4.2 Capacity building and supporting activities for R&I actors, in activities such as knowledge and good practices exchange as well as cooperation activities, the WP4 will interact and develop on coordination with the WP5 initiatives and objectives, on Networking of “international outreach”(as WP4 states in its objectives in the GA).

WP6 - Connecting research and policy making - Next generation policy tools (M6-M36)

This WP, led by ARDITI (Madeira) has its major connection with the WP4 in the Task 4.5, Operational and sustainability Strategy for OR's Officers. The Task 4.5 that interconnects on Task 6.3 - “Ensuring sustainability of long-term research activities in ORs”- in order to coordinate efforts to create the Regional Contact Points. Due to the foreseen close relation with the local governments and the needed Regional Governments committing for its implementation, bridging the governance to the scientific system by innovative policies in order to open new and better opportunities for OR for the next Framework Programme for Research and Technological Development.

WP8 – Communication and dissemination (M1-M36)

Also the WP8, on dissemination and communication, is an essential transversal tool along implementation of WP4, in order to give the necessary visibility and awareness to attain the

implementation of Task 4.5 Operational and sustainability Strategy for OR's Officers. Therefore WP8 should provide a summarized template to filled in with the event information, namely the event title, venue, day, organization responsible, speakers/trainers, 1 or 2 photos (group and trainer/speaker, during the event – with the FW images) , so that its published in our website and sent to the general media.

The capacity building actions within the FORWARD plan should be disseminated through the 'agenda' section, as in 'upcoming events' of the FORWARD website for an up-to-date source of information concerning FORWARD activities. The agenda of events should be disseminated through the FORWARD social networks and the newsletter included at task 8.5. This should be coordinated between the Regional Coordinators and the WPL8 with the supervision of the WP4L. The person in charge of uploading the events at FORWARD social media can be the Task 8.5 responsible, or a designated person, and it should be in contact with the WP8 Task leader for the website (NEXA) and the WP4 leader (FRCT).

WP4 Operationally

The WP4, as a Capacity Building FORWARD Work Package, is engaged in following the new trends on online learning skills, having the present needs and future needs as a reply to current constrains as the recent international health pandemic has demonstrated.

Capacity buildings should embrace this new digital challenge and invest more in learning methods as **e-Learning, web-seminars and podcasts**. The use of digital tools can also help to overcome our geographical constraints as Outermost Regions to a certain degree. Although the increasing value in using of digital tools, we should have in to account that the value of head-to-head meetings is essential to engage and potentiate interaction, adding value and potentiating the WP4 activities outcomes, as well as contributing for other WP synergies, as WP5 (networking). Therefore, even with the recognition of the growing importance of digital events, when possible the option of in-person participation should be privileged.

Fellowships

Considering the current situation with the COVID the travelling abroad may limit the possibility of complying with the Fellowships abroad, therefore the option of international trainings online should be taken in to consideration. These fellowships goals are international widening and capacitation and that should be assured that is attained by choosing the online option that should be clear in the impact and skills gained in the implementation report.

By enabling digital/online initiatives we promote and facilitate joint programming's and events, between OR's, as well as at a national and international level. As an example we have [DEVCO](#) programs, that are already promotes at a third Countries level. These methods facilitate the promotion of the exchange of good practices and knowledge from national organizations and the EC and the OR's, taking down the knowledge geographical barriers.

IMPLEMENTATION

IMPLEMENTATION

To implement the capacity-building plan and training activities in the OR's R&I ecosystem the WP4 will follow these steps:

- ✓ Task 4.1 - Design of Capacity Plan for EU Research Framework
- ✓ Task 4.2 - Capacity building and supporting activities for R&I actors
- ✓ Task 4.3 - Establishment of a network of dedicated OR R&I Officers
- ✓ Task 4.4 - Capacity Building for OR's Officers
- ✓ Task 4.5 - Operational and sustainability Strategy for OR's Officers

Figure 3, WP4 Roadmap. Source: WP4 leader presentation on WP4 methodology (FRCT)

In order to comply with the Deliverable 4.1 (and task 4.1), the WP4 leader asked the partners to gather the available training courses in their organizations and in the OR's, nationally and internationally during the year of 2019 and 2020, if any available, identified as of interest for the project goals in this WP. This exercise was useful to gather information on what were the capacity building actions that exist and as well to identify the gaps on training and capacity building activities. This list referred to 2019, to have a plan reference from a full year, was upload in to the FORWARD shared platform and served as a base of reference to construct the regional proposal for Capacity Building Plan for WP4. These exercise also allowed a wider view in order to identify potential interactions and twining events between OR's and within the R&I regional actors.

We should be aware that the COVID pandemic urgency may constrain in person events therefore the partners should try to find digital solutions or others in order to enable the realization of capacity actions and the fulfillment of the for the WP4 in general.

Methodology

As a preliminary exercise to be done by each FW partner in order to create a tailor made regional Capacity Plan is using as funding bases the inputs and events/initiatives/consultations organized for and with the regional R&I ecosystem.

The Regional Coordinator should be the privileged regional contact in representation of it's FW regional partners and should be in close communication with the WP4 leader in FORWARD project, namely to provide and manage the information regarding the activities taking place regionally and helping writing the reports. The WPL provides documents, namely a calendar, for the Regional Coordinator to update and managed – available on the google drive – for an overall follow-up of the WP.

The information's already gathered in the WP2 and on WP4 (2019 events table and Workshop with FW partners in Reunion Island) are a valuable source of multilevel information for the FORWARD Partners to build their regional Capacity Plan proposal.

The COVID situation has restricted the organization, in the desirable timing, of local on person events, therefore the partners have to resource to information that the FORWARD project has already produced until this moment.

In the WP2 it can be used the inputs from the R&I community from the interviews, surveys, and the regional workshop. Also regarding the WP4 there was already a previews exercise of analysis of the events organized in 2019, this list of capacity activities can be used as guiding lines, either to reinforce, to create or repeat the events identified as priority, in annex 5. Also during the project meeting in Saint Denis, in La Reunion, the leader of the WP4 organized an workshop for the partners in order to do a joint reflection on the OR's state of needs regarding capacity building, this resulted in the data that is reported in annex 6. This Workshop had 4 steps, the first 2 was an exercise of "evaluating capacities", were the partners had to do a self-

evaluation (step 1) and priorities (step 2), the next 2 steps are within the exercise of “identifying flows”, third step for “excellence knowledge” and as a last step the “financing”.

The first step regarding the self-evaluation was based on each participant experience, in the context of their ecosystem, as well as the analysis and conclusions from the inputs received from the R&I ecosystem regionally in WP2. This exercise of self-evaluation resulted in to a resumed table, post event, resumed by the WP4 leader that highlighted the most common matters that should be taken in to account. This resumed table gave a wider view of the strengths and needs in order to address the capacity and training plan. This information, individually and global, allowed the base to construct a suited roadmap that can lead each OR, within its specific regional characteristics, to attain the common goal for WP4 in FORWARD, namely of improving their performance regarding successful participation in R&I financed projects, in general, and in Framework-program, in particular.

Figure 4. Resume of the conclusions of the Step 1 of analysis of the Capacity needs for OR's in the FW project related to strengths and needs for capacity building Plan – a common view

Figure 5. Resume of the conclusions of the Step 2 of analysis of the Capacity priority, as a vision for the future for the ORs R&I community

Figure 6. Resumed conclusions regarding Step 3, on the lacks of excellence knowledge transfer in OR's in ORs R&I community – a common view

Figure 7. An example regarding Step 4 reflection on the identification of financing captation needed, having three regions conclusion as an example

These several exercises allowed not only to analyze individually each region necessities but also gain conscience on mutual/common needs and strength, this empowered a needed networking between the OR's partners. The 4 steps analyses was concluded as a road to construction of common trainings, taking in to account and respecting each OR's maturity and regional R&I reality and the following table was given, in order to analyze the capacity activities to include and privilege. The following questions were posed to the FORWARD partners participating in the workshop, as a way to build connection between exercises and conclude, as an ongoing work regionally:

1. Are the selected **priorities** answering to the present **needs** on your region's R&I ecosystem?
2. How the **lacks on excellence** conditioned the **finance access**? In what way?
3. Regarding the **financial flow**, in what way your OR can **build synergies** with other OR's in order to fill each other's gap?

Figure 8. Conclusion from the 4 steps in to an ongoing process of regional adaption of a common goal guidelines for WP4

The information that resulted from these joint exercises of reflection, in the workshop and from WP2 conclusions was the base to construct the D4.1. With orientation of the common guidelines a regional tailor made regional capacity plan proposal, in line with the GA budgeted and goals was presented.

The methodology post COVID had to be adjusted, from an in person event with representatives of the R&I community to an event organized by each 9 designated Regional Coordinator, that represent the OR in the project for WP4 works. The regional FORWARD partners analyses the extended information collected and analyzed and also had orientations to involve in the process of the creation of the Capacity Plan some regional key players from the R&I ecosystem, if possible taking in to consideration the COVID restrictions.

In case there was a decision on the part of the Regional Coordinator to involve in the final process of construction of a regional Capacity Building proposal external participants, to advise and give inputs on the Regional proposal for WP4, the following profile was given to the RC by the WP4 leader:

- ✓ Key player in the R&I ecosystem identified in the WP2 diagnose;

- ✓ An R&I actor that is integrated in the WP3 TWG, as Member, subcoordinator or facilitator;
- ✓ A significant level of international and European engagement in financed projects.

The size and actors to include in this initiative may vary by the asymmetries that were already identified by the WP2 diagnose and should be proposed by the Regional Coordinator and discussed/presented to its FORWARD regional partners.

The construction of the group and organization the meeting to construct the WP4 regional Capacity Plan should comply with the following rules:

- The proposal from the RC of the list of R&I actors, external to the FORWARD project, should be approved by the FORWARD partners, previously to contacting them;
- The number of these external actors should not overpass in double the total of the FORWARD regional partners. For example, Azores has 3 FW partners, therefore we should not invite more than 6 external actors from the R&I as guest participants in the meeting;
- The maximum number of participants should not overpass 10, in total - in order to keep a fluid and constructive debate on the online meetings - In case the RC, in coordination with the FW regional partners decide to have an “in person” meeting, this rules are flexible, as long as the Regional Coordinator assures the flow and desired outputs and results to take out of this WP4 meeting. Take in to account that each region may be subjected by restrictions policies regarding “in person” events due to COVID19.

Content and references

The GA already propose a list of trainings and capacity building initiatives that should be taken in to account in the OR’s capacity building and training Plan. Also there is a list presented by each FW partners regarding the training and capacity building actions, at a regional, national and international level in 2019, that are reunited by the orientation of the WP4 leader and available in the FORWARD google drive - these should serve as guides in the construction of the regional capacity Plan. The RC in coordination with the WP2 regional representative of the region should make available the all information described previously and make it available before and during the meeting.

As examples in the GA from capacity actions we have: "Project management and financial reporting of EC Projects"; “Writing H2020 successful proposals”; “Writing of the Impact

Section”; “Management, coordination and implementation of coordinated projects”; “ERC: How to design a successful proposal”; “MSCA: How to design a successful proposal”.

Although the number of actions on WP4 is limited to a previously defined the budgeted (as presented in table 1 and 2), it’s important to take in to consideration that more capacity actions and trainings are welcome as long as it uses other sources of existing financing for training and capacity that could be aligned with the FORWARD Capacity Plan goals, namely using the trainings offered by each National Contact Point.

	AZO	CAN	GUA	GU Y	MA D	MAR	MAY	RE U	SAI
Trainings/workshops for researchers on project management and development	3	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1
Workshops for R&I actors on proposal co-creation and project implementation	3	3	3	2	2	0	1	3	0
Trainings on scientific excellence in research	3	5	3	2	1	0	0	2	0
Trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	2	2	2	2	1	0	0	1	1
Researchers attending trainings abroad	5	10	7	20	20	6	0	10	0
R&I actors participating in the capacity actions	20	62	60	5	20	3	2	30	2
Regional meetings for MoU’s preparation	2	2	1	1	1	0	0	1	0

Table 3. WP4 implementation indicator, source: GA FORWARD

The implementation of the Regional Capacity Plan is closely followed by the Regional Coordinators, transmitted to the WP4 leader that in its turn will keep the coordinator of the project up to date regarding the development of the WP4 actions and any difficulties that may occur. The WP4 will keep a close communications with the WP7 leader (monitoring and evaluation) and WP8 leader for dissemination of the actions, namely in the FORWARD website and digital network.

Additionally, a series of Indicators, Milestone and Deliverables need to be produced according to GA (Summarized in Table 1). To facilitate the exchange of information between partners a database named WP4 Capacity and training Activities indicators (Annex 1) was created at

FORWARD Google Drive WP4 folder. This database contains 4 annexes and one power point with information on the WP4 objectives, as tools for construction, management and implementation. There will be also a common table for FW events/initiatives that register also actions that include synergies between WP, namely WP4-WP6, WP5-WP4-WP8, etc, that is to be created by the coordinator, as agreed in SC.

Following these objectives we made available the following tools for WP4 as a step by step construction and follow up of the WP4 Capacity Plan:

Information

WP4 Power point with the Guidelines and Methodology – to be presented in technical meeting with FOWARD partners and to be validated by the Steering Committee;

Annex 1 - Summarizes information on target activities per region of WP4 actions to be implemented - resumes Indicators of WP evolution to compare with those fixed in the Grant Agreement.

Construction

Annex 2 – Resumed list of the target actions per regions and per partner foreseen in the GA FORWARD budgeted.

Implementation

Annex 3 – Regional Capacity Plan proposal, to be completed by the RC and updated periodically (timeframe to be defined) to keep the WP4 leader informed;

Annex 4 – Follow up of actions on the WP4 Capacity and training actions. In this template each partner should report the actions that are foreseen in the GA as their minimum target action for this WP4 – with the description of the trainers bio, skills gained, type of target public, conclusions, photos, media information disseminated, etc.

Common Table on google drive - Actions follow up – common event templates. Information on the event executed under FORWARD project, per region and partner, to be gathered and managed regionally by each Regional Coordinator and be sent periodically to the WP leaders (timeframe to be defined per leader).

The information should be managed and centralized in the RC and reported to the WP4 leader – Proposal of a Regional Plan should be sent before the 2nd of July (02.06.2020) to the WP4 leader, taking in to account the delays that each region as suffered due to the COVID measures, the confinement and post-confinement measures of health safety. The Regional Coordinator is

responsible for gathering all the information and fill in the Annexes and other required information regarding the WP4, as well as reporting it to the WP4 leader. The RC should support the WP4 leader in reporting on WP4 activities.

Figure 9. Work Methodology on WP4. Source: WP4 leader, FRCT

The first step aims to implement the WP4 is through a regional design of Capacity Plan Proposal by a regional partners meeting – “in person” or online. The results should be coordinated and managed primarily by the Regional Coordinator with the collaboration of the FORWARD regional partners. The several steps of creation of a Capacity Plan are illustrated in Figure 10. and described in the methodology.

Figure 10. Methodology for the WP4 Capacity Plan Co-construction. Source: WP4 leader, FRCT¹

In order to create and propose a Regional Action Plan the timeframe was defined by the GA as M18, however and taking in to account the current pandemic of COVID the methodology had to be revised to change the initial “on person” Workshop designed for the methodology. Therefore, the defined deadline initially had to be changed and adjusted to a new reality that may affected the implementation of these actions.

Calendar proposal for WP4 co-construction – Task 4.1 & Task 4.2

ACTIONS	TIMELINE /DEADLINE
Publish the WP4 Guidelines and additional documents on the google drive	15 th May 2020
SC members appoint a Regional coordinator for the WP4 – one per OR	20 th May 2020
Receive inputs on the document – accessible on the Google drive	15 th - 21 th May 2020
Technical Web meeting with the WPL , specially WP3;WP5;WP6;WP8 - to aligne actions and strategies	18 th - 28 th May 2020
Technical Web meeting with the FW partners : WP4 leader present the methodology and discuss the inputs (made in advance) - validation	26 th /27 th /28 th May 2020
Adjust the methodology for COVID restrictions*	9 th to 19 th June
Send the adjusted WP4 methodology for comments and suggestions by FORWARD partners	23 th -25 th June 2020
SC Online voting - validate the WP4 Methodology and Guidelines and associated documents	25 th -26 th June 2020
Regional built of a regional Capacity Plan – coordinated and sent by RC for WP4 to the WP4 leader	26 th of June - 10 th July 2020
WPL validates the 9 action plan and send the final documents to the coordinator to comply with the D4.1 to send to the EC	10 th July 2020

*Due to COVID situation the D.4.2 had a delay of 4 months

Figure 11. Calendar for WP4 Capacity building and training activities (M6 - M36), power point presentation of the WP4 Guidelines, FRCT

¹ In base of the pyramid of the Methodology for the WP4 Capacity Plan Co-construction, in the figure 5, is the FORWARD WP2 diagnose and mapping to the R&I ecosystem's in the OR's, lead by NEXA; The self-evaluation regarding Capacity needs are the output from the WP4 Workshop lead by FRCT with the participation of FW partners, in representation of the OR's, in SC in Reunion Island in July 2019 – completed later on by Mayote

OPERATIONAL WORK PLAN

OPERATIONAL WORK PLAN

Task 4.1 Design of Capacity Plan for EU Research Framework (M6-M15)

The Task 4.1 Design of Capacity Plan for EU Research Framework (M6-M15) previews the creation of a common Capacity Plan in the OR's that will serve as a base for each region to co-design and propose a adapted Capacity Plan in order to respect and tailor the different maturity levels and experience of each region, since according to WP2 analysis are very diverse.

The WP4 Capacity Plan will address common issues in OR, with a methodological backbone, diagnosed by the WP2 and in WP4 workshop in Saint Denis, Reunion Island in July 2019. Although, due to the identified maturity levels of the 9 R&I ecosystems of the OR's, specially reflected in the 9 WP2 regional diagnoses, it justifies a regional implementation of a tailored capacity plan action.

This Plan should be build bottom up in each OR and be implement according to their capacity needs, as diagnosed in the WP2 – tables, interviews, surveys, WP2 workshops, etc. - and use also the information from WP4 workshop in La Reunion, organized by the FRCT with the participation of the FW partners. Periodical online meetings between a Regional Coordinator (that each region should appoint) and FORWARD regional partners, as well with WP4 leader, should allow the follow up of WP4 activities regionally.

The Regional Coordinator is responsible for following up the implementation of the Capacity Building Plan in each region by the FW regional partners. **The activities should be implemented by the consortium partner with competence in R&I policies and research.** The actions implemented per partners should involve and be communicated to the Regional Coordinator that will track these initiatives and request to each regional partner a report per action (templates to be made available in the google drive – common for all FW activities, as decided in May 2020 SC meeting).

The target public of the WP4 activities should be selected accordingly to the subject to be addresses and should privilege the participation of a mixed group of expertise and areas of work, within the quadruple helix logic, as well as take in to account the gender balance. **The Annex 3 has a table available to indicate the proposed title for the action; target public; goal & skills trainings. This table allows to have the full information regarding the actions to be implemented and filled in taking in to account the target information on targets on annex 2 – taking in to account the GA and each partners budgeted. These are tables per region to be completed by the Regional Coordinator.**

The actions on the Capacity Plan should be focused on the European R&I Framework (H2020, FP9) for R&I Ecosystems through different targets, as stated in the GA, with actions directed to:

1. Supporting researchers: activities will include specific trainings/workshops on i) project development ii) project management and iii) transfer scientific excellence iv) innovation entrepreneurship. Specially, aiming at improving Horizon 2020 knowledge and capacities within the research communities to respond adequately to the current and future EU Framework Programme

2. Fostering collaboration with companies, industry and cross-sectorial collaboration: capacity building will entail dedicated events and trainings, creation of spin-offs, public-private partnerships, etc., in close relation with the WP5 events of networking;
3. OR's Officers teams to better provide technical support to advice and orient R&I actors in EU Framework Program;
4. Special focus on accessing the SME instrument / reinforcing the participation of SME's in Framework Programmes. Through this specific trainings/campaigns SME's are powered on their capacity building actions that will help them develop FP projects;
5. Consolidating the FORWARD consortium through mutual learning and twining actions discussion.

Implemented actions

- ✓ Presentation of the WP4 roadmap during the Kick off meeting to the GA partners, February 2019 in Las Palmas, Canary Islands;
- ✓ Presentation of a draft proposal to partners on WP4 during a GA meeting online – on the 19th of June 2019- 10h30 Azores time/ 12h30 Brussels time;
- ✓ A Workshop session with FORWARD SC partners on WP4 Capacity Plan (M7) during the meeting in Reunion Island – France;
- ✓ A regional meetings with the FW partners and eventual R&I key partners, identified in the WP2.

Next steps

A Regional Coordinator should be appointed in representation of the OR's until the 14th of May 2020. **The Regional Coordinator should manage WP4 activities in their region and be in contact with the WP4 leader, to support coordination and follow up of the WP4 actions regionally.**

The WPL, in coordination with the Regional Coordinator, gathers inputs internally, from the FW partners, and externally, from the actors of the R&I ecosystem, to build the Capacity Building Plan– following the event in Reunion Island, with the SC partners, and the regional workshops that will take place in each OR. The way to tailor a Plan to each Region will be to start by analyzing the results of the interviews and surveys and combine this information from WP2 with a regional Workshop organized in each OR by the Regional Coordinator, with the FORWARD regional partners collaboration.

The inputs and concrete proposal of actions made by the stakeholders of the R&I should be the base of work of the FW regional partners, with the facilitation of the Regional Coordinators, in

order to present a regional final plan, privileging, and having as the step stone, the bottom up contributions.

As a result of this steps, gather information from WP2 interviews and surveys, organize a regional meeting (online or in person) and presentation of a final Regional Capacity Plan to the WP4 leader. The final result of this regional construction should be sent to the WP4 leader by the Regional Coordinator within the defined deadline (figure 11). The WPL for WP4 will gather the 9 OR's Capacity Plan and make it available to the all consortium. The implementation of the regional plan should be followed by the Regional Coordinator and report back to WP4 leader. This regional plans will be made available on the google drive in order for partners to identify possible synergies for implementation in the context of the FORWARD project and not only.

In the context of the previous steps the Regional Coordinators have to present to the WPL their proposal for Capacity Plan until 3th of July.

Following figure 10, on the Methodology for implementation of the WP4 Capacity Plan Co-construction, the first step to be implemented by each region should be the Regional meeting with the FOWARD Regional Partners (Point 1 from figure 10.). This meeting should be organized by the Regional Coodinator and fill in the annex 2, based on annex 1.

This first initiative to co-construct a tailor Capacity Plan can include the representation of the actors of quadruple helix of the R&I ecosystem (public sector; private sector; researcher and universities; and individuals from society with interest in R&I), namely the members of the WP3 thematic working Groups or other key partners that were identified in WP2 – however this events should take in to account it's efficiency and an alternative online method due to COVID pandemic and the following heath measures.

This Regional meeting should focus on **Identify priority of capacitation for the R&I regional actor**, based on information already collected and analyses by WP2 and the WP4 Workshop conclusions (in Reunion island SC meeting). In a second stage it's expected that the R&I community express those priorities in capacitation in a proposed action Plan.

This proposal should be aligned to the granted bugged in GA to the FORWARD regional partners in the project, as indicated by Annex 2 of this document. A table, based on annex 3, should be created, were each activity foreseen is indicated with type of action, associated with a proposal of title of action, as well as impacts (in terms of skills) and target public. This proposal should always have in to mind the goal of improving competences in EU programs and improving international outreach. For example, in Azores the FRCT foresees training and capacity action, so the actors may suggest that at least four should be a training with the title: "How to write a successful proposal", having as a target public in each one of these proposals the quadruple helix, with the goal of increasing submission of projects and to gain skills on using appealing language, value the important subjects depending on the call to reach the needed points in evaluation, etc.

As stated in WP4 it should be organized “an event directed to the regional I&I ecosystem to build bottom up the Capacity Building and training Plan, as a base for the construction of the final regional plan”, however and due to the COVID restrictions the option is to organize online meetings or in person meetings of a limited number of participants, following the measures of COVID restrictions in their countries.

The facilitator of the meeting– the Regional Coordinator or event organizer – should summarize the conclusions of the works and be responsible for the fill up of regional the table, following the model given in annex 4, for the Regional Capacity Plan proposal to deliver to the WP4 leader within the defined timeline, as defined in the calendar (Figure 11). The final proposal for Task 4.1 should include a general guideline and 9 tables of proposal for initiatives, goal and target audience to be organize in the regions by the responsible partners in R&I ecosystem.

Task 4.2 - Capacity building and supporting activities for R&I actors (M12-M36)

This task is dedicated to develop capacity building activities targeting R&I actors and it will aim at improving their competences in the European programs and foster their international outreach.

This Task foresees a large range of activities, that has as a main goal build skills and capacity for improving the OR’s participation in FP, as: **Trainings/workshops for researchers on EU Project Management and Project Development, for instance: "Project management and financial reporting of EC Projects"; "Writing H2020 successful proposals"; "Writing of the Impact Section"; "Management, coordination and implementation of coordinated projects"; "ERC: How to design a successful proposal"; "MSCA: How to design a successful proposal"; "Knowledge Transfer"; "Knowledge Protection".** Researchers will be supported to attend either trainings organized locally in the framework of the project or other trainings of excellence organized abroad. **Exchange Knowledge and cooperation activities will include trainings, seminars, webinars, MOOCs/online courses, and/or summer school activities.** The **digital activities will have special importance due to the current situation with the COVID19 pandemic**, although it should not be limited to digital and in person events should be made available.

The task foresees the promotion or **reinforcement of project management skills for officers in research institutions that offer technical support to scientific teams in order to monitor research calls, identify project partners, develop and manage EU funded research projects, and provide support with specific issues such as IPR management. Activities under this subtask will include training administrative staff in EU project management.**

In order to achieve the promotion and the sharing of information and best practices on management of EU FP programs, as well as other international programs activities for FORWARD partners, it is foreseen the organization of **mutual learning events and twinning actions.** These activities intend to **support the rapid and efficient involvement of OR partners**

in less used financing sources and H2020 projects, taking their specific interests and expertise into account and it's encouraged to use WP5 schemes or **possibility of cofound this action from other different sources, such as Marie Skłodowska Curie action (MSCA_ITN; MSCA_RISE and MSCA_CoFund), or other regional funds to support their universities and research organizations**. The organization of webinars and or **workshops should create synergies between Horizon 2020 and European Structural and Investment Funds with the intent to increase the impacts of research and innovation investments, push towards open innovation, creation of innovative ecosystems, and bring companies and regions into the knowledge economy**. Also, analyzing key success factors and barriers on building synergies will be a way of opening the dialogue on the present state and future solutions that will already piggybank on the WP2 initiatives. We can capitalize on the AB specialization and outreach to empower possible synergies, namely between ESIF and H2020 at the JRC.

In the context of this Task the WP5 will have an important role in maximizing the outcomes of WP4 by opening opportunities for exchange activities and events participation at a regional, inter-regional, national, European and international level. The activities foreseen in the Task 5.1, "organization of and participation of networking and brokerage events", give the OR's R&I actors the opportunity to advance from a state acquired in the WP4, of new and improved capacities, namely to identify opportunities and cease them, to a state of applying the new capacities and skills through the international outreach that will be granted by WP5 activities, namely on networking and brokerage events, promoting the constructions of future consortium's. The COVID situation may limit this synergy however is important to take in to account that we should not limit the WP4 activities to online, risking to compromise this synergy opportunity, this decision should take the regional health situation as a priority.

We should stress that it's encouraged, so that we may empower the implementation, that this activities should not be limited to the budget attributed to the Regional partners by FORWARD project, as it may also include in the plan other activities with no budget impact in the FORWARD organizations, as actions planned in the National Contact Points or organized trough other programs and projects that may offer capacity building activities that fulfil the objectives defined by FORWARD WP4. These activities should be included in the action plan as a part of the capacity plan for the region, since the ultimate goal is to achieve capacitation of the R&I actors and empower the all regional ecosystem.

Task 4.3 Establishment of a network of dedicated OR R&I Officers (M18-M36)

Under objective defined in Task 4.3 the WP4 leader intends to create conditions for the establishment of an OR R&I Officers network. This objective should be supported by the actions planned under the WP3, WP5 and WP6, requiring on this regard a close coordination between Work Package leaders. The beginning of a new period in the Framework Project also open up opportunities to gain leverages, by saying so this network could be proposed to be subsidize through ERDF + Horizon Europe (//Widening program or Regional contact points), and thus

work on the sustainability of the network and WP4. This action should be correlated with WP5 and WP6 actions, as to network and reach innovative policies for OR's R&I ecosystem.

As WP5 states in the GA “networking events to favors networking activities of ORs and encourage the establishment of new relationships, collaborations, and consortia for the development of project proposals.”, therefore building bridges between WP4 goals, namely in the goal establishing a network of dedicated OR R&I Officers, and WP5 will empower the results that are foreseen in this project and that correlate the actions from the different WP of the project. The same can be said regarding the WP6, that by “facilitate the dialogue between the research community and policy makers, at regional, national and EU level”, as stated in GA as a goal to this WP, can be better reach if the understanding, awareness and capabilities and fined tuned between the several levels of the ecosystem, benefiting of capacitation actions and network occasions to reach the needed bridges and understanding of the OR's R&I ecosystem.

This task envisions the creation of a network between the regional structures established and financed by the OR to give personalized support on the spot and in applicants' own languages. The idea is not to build from zero a new services/sector/organization but instead reach out to the Network of national NCP to ask for guidance in their organization and ways to create a sustainable network of OR officers and restructure regionally existent services that could benefit from the same level of information as national NCPs. This regional services would give professional support services operating regionally, as an essential component of Funding Programmes implementation dedicated to OR R&I Officers . This would promote an equal, consistent and a more customize support to the specificities of regional research and innovation actors' in OR's in participating in Research Framework Programmes.

The work developed in this task intends to focus on building capacities to the OR R&I Officers, so that they can raise awareness, giving specialist advice, and provide on-the-ground guidance, close to the actors of the R&I ecosystem, in order to make EU Funding Programmes known – namely the interest/advantages of applying - and accessible to all potential applicants from the quadruple helix.

This task intends to create conditions and prepare Regional Governments to implement, from existing services, a reconstruction of a OR's R&I office, since this stage will be closely linked with the WP5 (networking) and the WP6 activities (innovative policies for researchers and R&I ecosystem). The last step will be the signature of a **Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)** by every region in order to enable the creation of a **Network of OR R&I Officers**.

As a fundamental step, previously to the Memorandum of Understanding, it's expected that each partner gathers information regarding existing OR's regional structures, at a public level, that support and develop activities in Framework programs and EU Fundings Programmes, in order to assess the existing organizations and human resources in order to capacitate and restructure services that allow the creation of a network of dedicated OR R&I Officers. This census should be made at least two months before the signing of the MoU, by the WP4 responsible in coordination with the regional representative of the FORWARD project (in case they do not coincide).

The goal & skills training on this Task should create competences in OR's R&I officers, as in parallel to build awareness in the decision makers, at a national and regional level, regarding the opportunities and a space that OR's can gain by sharing innovative ideas and build joint future solutions to better bridge the decision making process to technical application of the procedures to highlight to the EU and internationally the R&I capacities in the OR's.

Piggy-backing the **WP5 and WP6 activities**, contacts, discussions and official agreements will be made to establish all necessary conditions for the fully commitment of each Regional Government to implement an OR's R&I office. The last step will be the signature of a **MoU** by every region for the **Network of OR R&I Officers**.

This initiative should have a big media and social media coverage, in the context and with the support/coordination of the WP8 leader, in order to involve and promote the importance of this initiative, as a result of the FORWARD project and as a seed that will preside the project itself – also showcasing the value of H2020 programs, having FORWARD as a positive example.

Task 4.4 Capacity Building for OR's Officers (M24-M36)

FORWARD project aim with this Task to provide the OR's Officers teams the necessary training to develop the services expected from the OR's Officers, through the following actions:

1. Understanding the specificities of their R&I ecosystems to provide a customize guidance on choosing relevant H2020 topics and types of action;
2. Advice on administrative procedures and contractual issues
3. Training and assistance on proposal writing
4. Distribution of documentation (forms, guidelines, manuals etc.)
5. Assistance in partner search promoting international networking activities and collaborations.

These trainings should **be implemented in close relation and in collaboration with the National Contact Points of each Member state and will take in to account the outputs of the thematic working groups (WP3) in terms of recommendations, for partners research, priority calls and actions to implement in order to promote R&I**. This task allows also the link and participation of the OR's Officer teams at the European and National Open days.

The goal & skills training are finding a consortium (main partners; OR's; MAC..) to writing a proposal (rules on H2020 proposals) and submitting it successfully. In this context, and following the WP2 results the OR's **should focus on the Champion organizations on H2020 in the areas identified as priority for each region (based also in S3 – Smart Specialization), with the support of the WP3 experts that can help the OR's R&I partners with contacts in their areas of expertise, but also with the support of WP5 (Networking)**, in order to implement these activities with the necessary **international outreach** (regional; inter-OR; European; international).

Task 4.5 Operational and sustainability Strategy for OR's Officers (M24-M36)

This Task is focus on the **development of a Strategic Roadmap for the implementation of the OR's Regional offices**. This Task will depend on political conditions and priorities. Also this task aims at producing support documents to build the OR's R&I Network Offices - a Manual of Operational Guidelines for OR R&I Offices - for the implementation of these offices, in close relation with the local governments, and in coordination with the activities and results of the WP6. This will be made through the signing of the MoU for implementation of support within their respective governmental organizations a Strategy for OR's Officers.

The **Manual of Operational Guidelines for OR R&I Offices** should include the description of key principles, minimum standards and actions of the Offices, in coordination with the OR's, trough it's Regional Coordinator.

The target audience of this task should be primarily decision makers in the OR's therefore the WP4 actions should be in coordination of actions with WP6, primarily, but also with WP5 and WP3. A good synergies and alignment between WP's will be fundamental to produce the defined goals in this task.

OUTCOMES AND CONCLUSIONS

OUTCOMES AND CONCLUSION

The outcomes foreseen for the D4.1 in the GA are based on the “diagnostic and mapping results of the OR’s R&I Ecosystems in WP2 and on the first draft of the deliverable 2.5. A common vision for the OR’s R&I improvement the WP4 aims to stimulate and reinforce the R&I capabilities by empowering the ORs R&I actors with the adequate capacities to support and achieve their effective participation into the European R&I Framework Programmes (H2020, FP9 and others). “ This broader vision allowed the FW partners to have a common vision on OR’s capacity requirements, as also analyze in deep their own regional reality and reach out their R&I network to listen to their needs and expectations.

The WP2 started what WP4 will continue, an improvement of the cooperation that will in this stage of the D4.1 tackles the improvement of the skills and capacities of the actors of their R&I communities and current performance in FP programs. The all methodology proposed points to the promotion of the knowledge transfer within the quadruple helix regionally and gives space to synergies. The adaptation possibility of the adaptation of a general proposal do regional tailor made plans will give higher chances to each OR to boost their economic value chains, with a personalized plan, adjusted to each reality.

The Capacity Building plan will be implemented in each region by the consortium partner with competences in R&I policies and research. The implementation and support of the WP4 Plan will have a Regional Coordinator that keeps the link with the WP4 leader and allows a closer follow up of the unfold of the regional plan.

The specific objectives for this WP are assured by the proposals as a all, since it checks the following point:

- A Regional Plan was designed and is ongoing, foreseeing activities that target the main R&I actors, namely individual researchers, research organizations and companies.
- Capacity building activities not only aim at increasing researchers’ skills for their participation in EU research projects but also at facilitating collaboration and partnerships within and among research and innovation actors in the ORs.
- It has included in the Plans training to Spreading Research excellence and supporting the scientific production of a singular and high impact research at European and International level.

- The global impact that is intended with the Capacity Building Plan is structured in a way to equip the ORs with common and strategic capacities and skills to enable them to seize opportunities and participate in the European R&I framework programs and internationally, as well as foster international outreach & ORS regional officers and network. T

The improvement of the OR's network is also ensured by foreseen common activities, as the own that took place with the WP4 workshop that allowed a common knowledge and the arise of common training activities, namely in Brussels.

This deliverable plays a major role in the kick of the WP4 work package, as the foundation of this Works Package.

The COVID reality restrained the implementation of this work package that relies in actions that gathers participants in person, therefore it was needed to adjust the methodology and preview online events. Although this enables the implementation it has also an impact when it comes to synergies between WP, namely between the WP5 and the WP4, restricting the full advantages that were foreseen to take out of the implemented actions.

The methodology presented with the D4.1 in the WP4 is an approach to the OR'S R&I Ecosystem based on the present conditions, diagnosed by the WP2, of each R&I ecosystem in the OR's, but it also points to the future of what OR's R&I ecosystem can achieve trough training and capacitation, strengthening an OR's joint strategy for the future. Concluding in a positive note, the D4.1 will be the stepping stone that will promote a strong start for the WP4 actions. These can impact the raise of excellence in the OR's R&I ecosystem beyond FORWARD timeline, taking in to account that it's designed to promote actions for awareness and engagement of the decision makers and researchers, as well as all the quadruple helix and ultimately creating a better understanding and commitment between the OR's R&I ecosystems.

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- VI. *Mutual Learning Event Report*, FORWARD project (NEXA), 2019
- VII. *Common technical position of the OR S3 Network regarding Component 5 – Interregional innovation investments*, March 31st of 2017, the Presidents of the Outermost Regions (ORs)

Power Point presentation: GUIDELINES & METHODOLOGY FOR WP4

This power point presentation of the WP4: Capacity building and training activities (M6 - M36) is a resumed and illustrative version of the guidelines and methodology in the previews descriptive document. This presentation was used in the Steering Committee of the FORWARD project, as well as in the Technical Meeting with FORWARD partners and is also a easy to use guide to follow up for the FORWRAD partners WP4 activities and alignment with the defined goals and vision.

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GOVERNO DOS AÇORES

FRCT

GUIDELINES & METHODOLOGY

WP4: Capacity building and training activities (M6 - M36)

WP4 leader:
Regional Found for Science and Technology (FRCT)-Azores

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824550.

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GOVERNO DOS AÇORES

FRCT

WP 4 - Capacity building and training activities

Rational & objectives

FORWARD Objective

- ✓ Improving Outermost regions research and innovation (R&I) ecosystems' performance to increase participation in EU Framework Programmes

WP4 Objective:

- ✓ Implement a Capacity Building Plan in OR's that supports and builds competences in the R&I ecosystem on EU programmes, international outreach & ORS regional officers and network

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824550.

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WP4 – Methodology’s principles

Common Plan with tailored implementation

Common guidelines, tools and information, continuous support by FRCT to FW partners and in coordination with a Regional Coordinator per each OR

Flexible

A level of implementation is adapted according to the R&I needs, opening space to find other resources mobilized by partners for further capacity activities.

Synergies to build capacities

Promotes cross-sectorial collaboration, as well as between OR's, at a national, EU and Third countries level, namely with FP champions' to create competences in EU programmes and strengthen international outreach

Sustainable network for sustainable knowledge growth

A capacity building plan for the OR R&I in order to create a network of empowered regions for better common results

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 10101502

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WP4 – Methodology’s organization

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 10101502

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Organization of the meeting for the construction of the WP4 Regional Capacity Building Plan (I)

Organization of the meeting for the construction of the WP4 Regional Capacity Building Plan (II)

The construction of the group and organization the meeting to construct the WP4 regional Capacity Plan should comply with the following rules:

- ✓ The list of R&I actors is proposed by the RC and approved by the FORWARD regional partners;
- ✓ The number should not overpass in double the total of the FORWARD regional partners (except in the case the number of regional FW partners are 2 or 1);
- ✓ The total number should not overpass 10;
- ✓ The meeting can be “in person” or online – however due to the current situation of COVID the online option is encouraged.

Organization of the meeting for the construction of the WP4 Regional Capacity Building Plan (III)

The representatives from Regional R&I should comply with the following profile:

- ✓ To be key player in the R&I ecosystem identified in the WP2 diagnose;
- ✓ Should be an R&I actor that is integrated in the WP3 TWG, as Member, subcoordinator or facilitator;
- ✓ Have a significant level of international and European engagement in financed projects.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019720.

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WP4: Beyond common goals – a tailored Capacity Plan

- ✓ SETP 1: SELF EVALUATION
- ✓ STEP 2: PRIORITIES
- ✓ STEP 3: REGIONAL CAPACITY PLAN

PROPOSAL

Co-creation process of the Capacity Building Plan

A full circle process that combines common and ajusted actions to the 9 OR's R&I ecosystems

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019720.

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Calendar proposal for WP4 co-construction – Task 4.1 & Task 4.2

ACTIONS	TIMELINE /DEADLINE
Publish the WP4 Guidelines and additional documents on the google drive	15 th May 2020
SC members appoint a Regional coordinator for the WP4 – one per OR	20 th May 2020
Receive inputs on the document – accessible on the Google drive	15 th - 21 th May 2020
Technical Web meeting with the WPL , specially WP3;WP5;WP6;WP8 - to aligne actions and strategies	18 th - 28 th May 2020
Technical Web meeting with the FW partners : WP4 leader present the methodology and discuss the inputs (made in advance) - validation	26 th /27 th /28 th May 2020
Adjust the methodology for COVID restrictions*	9 th to 19 th June
Send the adjusted WP4 methodology for comments and suggestions by FORWARD partners	23 th -25 th June 2020
SC Online voting - validate the WP4 Methodology and Guidelines and associated documents	25 th -26 th June 2020
Regional built of a regional Capacity Plan – coordinated and sent by RC for WP4 to the WP4 leader	26 th of June - 10 th July 2020
WPL validates the 9 action plan and send the final documents to the coordinator to comply with the D4.1 to send to the EC	10 th July 2020

*Due to COVID situation the D.4.2 had a delay of 4 months

Introduction

WP4 Tool kit

Construction

ANNEX 1

Guidelines and Methodology for WP4

Information on targets

ANNEX 2

Proposal based on target actions per regions

ANNEX 3

Regional Plan Proposal - RC

ANNEX 4

Template for WP4 action description

Actions follow up and report - templates

Implementation

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IMPLEMENTATION

WP4 – per Task

Task 4.1 Design of Capacity Plan for EU Research Framework

Timeline: M06 - M15

Initiatives:

- ✓ Presentation of a draft proposal (M6);
- ✓ Workshop session with FORWARD partners on WP4 Capacity Plan (M7) – La Reunion
- ✓ Regional tailor made proposal to the OR's R&I ecosystem needs

Main goal: A common Capacity Plan designed to orient and define the capacity building actions to be implemented in a diversified and adapted way in each OR by the consortium partner with competence in R&I policies and research

Target audience: OR's partners and Regional R&I ecosystem

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150

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IMPLEMENTATION

WP4 – per Task

Task 4.2 Capacity building and supporting activities for R&I actors

Timeline: M12 - M36

Initiatives:

- ✓ Training sessions
- ✓ Workshops
- ✓ Online events

Main goal: Reinforce skills & promote the sharing of information at regional and European level of best practices on management of EU FP programs as well as other international programs.

Target audience: EU Project Management and Project Development (private sector; researchers; public officers, SME's)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150

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IMPLEMENTATION WP4 – per Task

Task 4.3 Establishment of a network of dedicated OR's R&I Officers

Timeline: M18 - M36

Initiatives:

- ✓ Census on the existing R&I organizations in the OR's
- ✓ Good practices and experience sharing on previous FP
- ✓ Working session
- ✓ Initiatives in close relation/in synergy with WP5 (networking) and WP6 (involve decision makers)

Main goal: creating the conditions for the establishment an OR R&I Officers network; signature of a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) by every region for the Network of OR R&I Officers

Target audience: R&I Officers – project managers at several levels of the regional and national governmental structure; Decision makers at a regional & national level

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IMPLEMENTATION WP4 – per Task

Task 4.4 Capacity Building for OR's Officers

Timeline: M24 - M36

Initiatives:

- ✓ Trainings to reinforce skills of OR's Officers
- ✓ Assistance in partner's search in order to promote international network & synergies (close to WP5 and WP3 activities)
- ✓ Participation of the OR's Officer team at the European and National Open days
- ✓ Trainings in close relation and in collaboration with the NCPs of each Member state

Main Goal: Provide to OR's Officers teams the necessary training to develop the services expected from the OR's Officers

Target audience: OR's Officer

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 624550.

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IMPLEMENTATION WP4 – per Task

Task 4.5 Operational and sustainability Strategy for OR's Officers

Timeline: M24 - M36

Initiatives:

- ✓ Public Forum

Main goal: Strategic Roadmap for the implementation; Manual of Operational Guidelines for OR R&I Offices; Promote and advocate the restructuring of existing R&I organization's/HR to build a OR's network to support the FP participation of the R&I ecosystem

Target audience: Regional and local governments; Regional Officers

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

WP4 EXPECTED OUTCOMES

Promote effective **participation** in the European R&I Framework Programs trough the improvement of competences

Foster international **outreach** & **ORS regional officers and network**

Capacity building activities goals

Promote & empower capabilities of project management offices in research institutions

Exchange Knowledge and cooperation activities

Webinars/workshops on synergies between Horizon 2020 and European Structural and Investment Funds

Trainings/workshops for researchers on EU Project Management and Project Development,

Mutual learning events; twinning actions proposal for FORWARD partners to reinforce OR's network

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

**THANK YOU
OBRIGADA
GRACIAS
MERCÍ**

WP4 leader: FRCT (Azores)

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

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ANNEX 1: Information's in GA regarding WP4

FORWARD - WP4 INFORMATIONS		
Work package 4 title:	Capacity building and training activities	
Lead beneficiary	FRCT	
Timeframe for implementation	M6_JUN2019 - M36_DEC2021	
Milestone 5	Month 18_JUN2020	Capacity building plan and common training programme for capacity building activities
Deliverables 4.1	Month 18_JUN2020	Capacity building plan
Deliverables 4.2:	Month 18_JUN2021	Common training programme for OR's R&I actors
Deliverable 4.3:	Month 25_JAN2020	Common training programme for OR's R&I officers
Deliverable 4.4:	Month 36_DEC2021	OR R&I Offices Operational and Sustainability Strategic for implementation

WP4 global indicators

CAPACITY ACTIVITIES	AZO	CAN	GUA	GUY	MAD	MAR	MAY	REU	SAI
Trainings/workshops for researchers on project management and development	3	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	1
Workshops for R&I actors on proposal co-creation and project implementation	3	3	3	2	2	0	1	3	0
Trainings on scientific excellence in research	3	5	3	2	1	0	0	2	0
Number of trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	2	2	2	2	1	0	0	1	1
Number of researchers attending trainings abroad	5	10	7	20	20	6	0	10	0
Number of R&I actors participating in the capacity actions	20	62	60	5	20	3	2	30	2
Number of regional meetings for MoU's preparation	2	2	1	1	1	0	0	1	0

WP4 Indicators per region

The indicators allowed each partner Region to have in to mind what are the initiatives and correspondent budgeted in the GA for WP4 activities to start building their Regional Capacity plan proposals.~

REGION		PARTNERS				
Capacity Activities	TOTAL	Partner	Capacity activities Type	Total number	Buged per activity	Total Budgeted
Trainings/workshops for researchers on project management and development	3	FRCT	Trainings	6	2 500,00 €	15 000,00 €
Workshops for R&I actors on proposal co-creation and project implementation	3		Fellowships to attend trainings abroad	3	1 500,00 €	4 500,00 €
Trainings on scientific excellence in research	3	UAC	Trainings	3	2 500,00 €	7 500,00 €
Trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	2		Fellowships	2	1 500,00 €	3 000,00 €
Researchers attending trainings abroad	5	CCIA	Trainings	2	2 500,00 €	5 000,00 €
R&I actors participating in the capacity actions	20					
Regional meetings for MoU's preparation	2					
					TOTAL	35 000,00 €

REGION		PARTNERS				
Capacity Activities	TOTAL	Partner	Capacity activity type	Total number	Buged per activity	Total Budgeted
Trainings/workshops for researchers on project management and development	2	GOBOCAN	Trainings	2	2 500,00 €	5 000,00 €
Workshops for R&I actors on proposal co-creation and project implementation	3	ULL	Trainings	2	2 500,00 €	5 000,00 €
Trainings on scientific excellence in research	5		Fellowships to attend trainings abroad	2	1 500,00 €	3 000,00 €
Trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	2	ULPGC	Trainings	2	2 500,00 €	5 000,00 €
Researchers attending trainings abroad	10		Fellowships to attend trainings abroad	2	1 500,00 €	3 000,00 €
R&I actors participating in the capacity actions	62	PLOCAN	Trainings	2	2 500,00 €	5 000,00 €
Regional meetings for MoU's preparation	2		Fellowships to attend trainings abroad	2	1 500,00 €	3 000,00 €
		ITC	Trainings	2	2 500,00 €	5 000,00 €
			Fellowships to attend trainings abroad	2	1 500,00 €	3 000,00 €
		IAC	Trainings	2	2 500,00 €	5 000,00 €
			Fellowships to attend trainings abroad	2	1 500,00 €	3 000,00 €
		CE	no budgeted on GA for WP4 activities	0	- €	- €
					TOTAL	45 000,00 €

FORWARD - GUADALUPE WP4 INDICATORS

REGION		PARTNERS				
Capacity Activities	TOTAL	Partner	Capacity activities Type	Total number	Buged per activity	Total Budgeted
Trainings/workshops for researchers on project management and development	2	REG GUA	Trainings	5	2 500,00 €	12 500,00 €
Workshops for R&I actors on proposal co-creation and project implementation	3		Fellowships to attend trainings abroad	6	1 500,00 €	9 000,00 €
Trainings on scientific excellence in research	3	UA	Trainings	5	2 500,00 €	12 500,00 €
Trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	2		Fellowships to attend trainings abroad	2	1 500,00 €	3 000,00 €
Researchers attending trainings abroad	7				TOTAL	37 000,00 €
R&I actors participating in the capacity actions	60					
Regional meetings for MoU's preparation	1					

FORWARD - GUYANE WP4 INDICATORS

REGION		PARTNERS				
Capacity Activities	TOTAL	Partner	Capacity activities Type	Total number	Buged per activity	Total Budgeted
Trainings/workshops for researchers on project management and development	2	CTG	Trainings	4	2 500,00 €	10 000,00 €
Workshops for R&I actors on proposal co-creation and project implementation	2		Fellowships to attend trainings abroad	8	1 500,00 €	12 000,00 €
Trainings on scientific excellence in research	2	UG	Trainings	2	2 500,00 €	5 000,00 €
Trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	2		Fellowships to attend abroad trainings	6	1 500,00 €	9 000,00 €
Researchers attending trainings abroad	20		Trainings	2	2 500,00 €	5 000,00 €
R&I actors participating in the capacity actions	5	GDI	Fellowships to attend trainings abroad	6	1 500,00 €	9 000,00 €
Regional meetings for MoU's preparation	1	SYNERGILE	no budgeted on GA for WP4 activities	0	- €	- €
					TOTAL	50 000,00 €

FORWARD - MADEIRA WP4 INDICATORS

REGION		PARTNERS				
Capacity Activities	TOTAL	Partner	Capacity activities Type	Total number	Buged per activity	Total Budgeted
Trainings/workshops for researchers on project management and development	2	ARDITTI	Trainings	4	3 500,00 €	14 000,00 €
Workshops for R&I actors on proposal co-creation and project implementation	2		Fellowships to attend trainings abroad	10	1 500,00 €	15 000,00 €
Trainings on scientific excellence in research	1	UMA	Trainings	2	3 500,00 €	7 000,00 €
Trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	1		Fellowships to attend trainings abroad	10	1 500,00 €	15 000,00 €
Researchers attending trainings abroad	20				TOTAL	51 000,00 €
R&I actors participating in the capacity actions	20					
Regional meetings for MoU's preparation	1					

FORWARD - MARTINIQUE WP4 INDICATORS

REGION		PARTNERS				
Capacity Activities	TOTAL	Partner	Capacity activities Type	Total number	Buged per activity	Total Budgeted
Trainings/workshops for researchers on project management and development	1	CTM	Trainings	1	2 500,00 €	2 500,00 €
Workshops for R&I actors on proposal co-creation and project implementation	0		Fellowships to attend trainings abroad	5	1 500,00 €	7 500,00 €
Trainings on scientific excellence in research	0				TOTAL	10 000,00 €
Trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	0					
Researchers attending trainings abroad	6					
R&I actors participating in the capacity actions	3					
Regional meetings for MoU's preparation	0					

REGION		PARTNERS				
Capacity Activities	TOTAL	Partner	Capacity activities Type	Total number	Buged per activity	Total Budgeted
Trainings/workshops for researchers on project management and development	1	CDM	Trainings	2	2 500,00 €	5 000,00 €
Workshops for R&I actors on proposal co-creation and project implementation	1				TOTAL	5 000,00 €
Trainings on scientific excellence in research	0					
Trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	0					
Researchers attending trainings abroad	0					
R&I actors participating in the capacity actions	2					
Regional meetings for MoU's preparation	0					

REGION		PARTNERS				
Capacity Activities	TOTAL	Partner	Capacity activities Type	Total number	Buged per activity	Total Budgeted
Trainings/workshops for researchers on project management and development	2	NEXA	Trainings	5	2 500,00 €	12 500,00 €
Workshops for R&I actors on proposal co-creation and project implementation	3		Fellowships to attend trainings abroad	6	1 500,00 €	9 000,00 €
Trainings on scientific excellence in research	2	UR	Trainings	3	2 500,00 €	7 500,00 €
Trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	1		Fellowships to attend trainings	4	1 500,00 €	6 000,00 €
Researchers attending trainings abroad	10				TOTAL	35 000,00 €
R&I actors participating in the capacity actions	30					
Regional meetings for MoU's preparation	1					

REGION		PARTNERS				
Capacity Activities	TOTAL	Partner	Capacity activities Type	Total number	Buged per activity	Total Budgeted
Trainings/workshops for researchers on project management and development	1	COMSM	Trainings	2	2 500,00 €	5 000,00 €
Workshops for R&I actors on proposal co-creation and project implementation	0	CCISM	no budgeted on GA for WP4 activities	0	- €	- €
Trainings on scientific excellence in research	0				TOTAL	5 000,00 €
Trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	1					
Researchers attending trainings abroad	0					
R&I actors participating in the capacity actions	2					
Regional meetings for MoU's preparation	0					

Effort per partner in WP4

This annex also mentions the effort allocated to the Work Package 4 efforts in human resources (PM).

FORWARD - WP4 PM effort per Partner					
Partner number and short name	WP4 effort				
1 - GOBCAN	3.00				
2 - FRCT	16.00				
3 - ARDITI	5.50				
4 - NEXA	6.00				
5 - CTM	5.00				
6 - CTG	3.90				
7 - REG GUA	5.50				
8 - COMSM	2.00				
9 - CDM	2.60				
10 - ULL	3.80				
11 - ULPGC	0.75				
FCPCT ULPGC	4.50				
12 - PLOCAN	3.80				
13 - ITC	3.80				
14 - IAC	3.80				
15 - UAc	5.00				
16 - CCIA	3.00				
17 - UMa	5.00				
18 - UR	6.00				
19 - UA	2.00				
20 - UG	3.00				
21 - GDI	2.50				
22 - Synergile	2.00				
23 - CCISM	1.50				
24 - CE	0.50				
Total 100.45					
Source: GA FORWARD					

ANNEX 2: Capacity Plan Proposal for FORWARD project – 9 Regional Capacity Plans OR

The Annex 2 was made available by the WP leader, based on the allocated budget in GA for WP4 activities in the FORWARD project. These were filled in by each WP4 Regional Coordinator in coordination with their regional FW partners. The following tables are indicative activities for proposal for WP4 and resulted from a regional co-construction.

Azores

AZORES - Capacity Training Proposal (WP4-FORWARD project)					
FW Partner	Capacity activity defined by FW GA	Proposed title for the action	Target public	Goal & Skills training	OBSERVATIONS
FRCT	Training_1	Workshop Plan Forward	Quadruple helix - R&I regional community	Proposal of actions for WP4; exchange of experience; reconstruction of a Regional Capacity Plan proposal	09 March 2020, in SM Island, Portugal
	Training_2	Green Deal Challenges	Universities; actors of the R&I community in the region; EMA	Call on specific areas; Share of expertise in framework programs; SDG in Framework Programs; Coaching in Leadership - the new leadership mindset	In partnership with regional S3
	Training_3	Beyond Outermostness - INNOVATION FORWARD	SME; EMA (space station); stakeholders in innovation	Innovation literacy - know about innovation networks; calls opportunities in FP and beyond	to be defined
	Training_4	Capacitação em Rede - Networking to excellence	Researchers and Experts in R&I ecosystem	Exchange on good practice in networking and examples of success; gain new insight regarding european consortium building.	To define synergy with one or more FW partner(s)
	Training_5	Info Days in R&I public policies (Regional S3-FORWARD)	Thematic approach per R&I groups on thematic identified in FORWARD as priority (WP3) - synergies with the regional S3	Training in how to apply to calls and manage projects. How to network for consortium building - thematic approach	Thematic approach; S3 synergies with FORWARD - align with the FORWARD
	Training_6	Info Days in R&I public policies (Regional S3-FORWARD)	Thematic approach per R&I groups on thematic identified in FORWARD as priority (WP3) - synergies with the regional S3	Training in how to apply to calls and manage projects. How to network for consortium building - thematic approach	Thematic approach; S3 synergies with FORWARD - align with the FORWARD
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_1	Communication in Science - Social Media and Writing for the Social Web	OR's Officers	Provide science communications professionals with online writing skills, teach practical skills on how to engage the public in science research on social media and learn how to turn academic research into accessible content for websites, blogs, videos and podcasts.	28-29 January 2020, Lisbon, Portugal
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_2	Advanced Training Skills	OR's Officers	Networking and Call identification and application	Brussels, Belgium
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_3	Advanced Training Skills	OR's Officers	Networking and Call identification and application	Brussels, Belgium
UA	Training_1	Introduction to Horizon Europe	Researches	Ensure know-how to participate in the FP and increase the number of proposals	to be defined
	Training_2	Financial rules of H2020 and Horizon Europe	Researches	Training of project managers: participation in FP / Optimizing financial excellence / Knowledge of new forms of cost "Lump Sump"	to be defined
	Training_3	HORIZON EUROPE: 2021-2027	Researches	Ensure know-how to participate in future FP and increase the number of proposals / Increase regional knowledge about specific calls, among other aspects	to be defined
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_1	Training in Madeira/Canarias	Researches	Improve the training of researchers / project managers and their network level	Madeira/Canarias
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_2	Training in Madeira/Canarias	Researches	Improve the training of researchers / project managers and their network level	Madeira/Canarias
	CCIA	Training_1	Innovation and Cooperation between stakeholders	Decision makers from companies and R&D organizations	Further analysis of the ability for business innovation opportunities and to contribute for the definition strategies to incorporate R&D for an ongoing/active business innovative processes and corporate policy. EU approach on funding for companies and European programs, opportunities and challenges for regional companies.
Training_2		Technologic and innovation applications in traditional companies (SMEs)	Traditional companies (SMEs) with low technological indicators or reduced innovation policies/plans	Reinforce the connection of local businesses to technological and R&D centers in order to allow the integration of (SMEs), traditional companies, in programs and ventures in order to increase innovation in their strategic plans for products/services development. EU approach on funding for business and cooperation programs. Opportunities and challenges for regional companies.	Location:Terceira Island. Public attendance and online transmission. 4 hours workshop

Canary Islands

CANARY ISLANDS - Capacity Training Proposal (WP4-FORWARD project)					
FW Partner	Capacity activity defined by FW GA	Proposed title for the action	Target public	Skills and Knowledge to attain	OBSERVATIONS
GOBCAN	Training_1	Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) funding opportunities and proposal preparation	1) SMEs (CEO) 2) SMEs (EU Project Managers) 3) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners 4) Technicians / Innovation managers 5) Clusters	BASIC/INTERMEDIATE: SUPP OR'S OFFICERS TEAMS & EU PROJECT MANAGERS FROM FW PARTNERS: Increase the participation in FP; e.g. writing successful R&I proposals; how to find EU opportunities; Introduction to HE; Management and coordination of EC-funded projects	Dependant on government measures regarding COVID-19
	Training_2	Proposal preparation to lever Interregional cooperation for SMES and Cluster	1) SMEs (CEO) 2) SMEs (EU Project Managers) 3) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners 4) Technicians / Innovation managers 5) Clusters	BASIC/INTERMEDIATE: SUPP OR'S OFFICERS TEAMS & EU PROJECT MANAGERS FROM FW PARTNERS: Increase the participation in FP; e.g. writing successful R&I proposals; how to find EU opportunities; Introduction to HE; Management and coordination of EC-funded projects	Dependant on government measures regarding COVID-19
ULL	Training_1	Writing successful MSCA proposals	1) Researchers from FW-CAN partners 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	INTERMEDIATE/ADVANCED: SUPP RESEARCHERS: Increase the participation of other R&I actors in FP (universities, research centers; public administration...) + SUPP OR'S OFFICERS TEAMS & EU PROJECT MANAGERS FROM FW PARTNERS: Human Resources, attraction and retaining R&I talent	Dependant on government measures regarding COVID-19
	Training_2	Introduction to HE	All	BASIC/INTERMEDIATE: SUPP RESEARCHERS: Increase the participation of other R&I actors in FP (universities, research centers; public administration...) + SUPP OR'S OFFICERS TEAMS & EU PROJECT MANAGERS FROM FW PARTNERS: Increase the participation in FP	Dependant on government measures regarding COVID-19
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_1	Collaborative projects in HE (RIA, IA, CSA)	1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	INTERMEDIATE/ADVANCED: SUPP RESEARCHERS: Increase the participation of other R&I actors in FP (universities, research centers; public administration...)	Dependant on government measures regarding COVID-19
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_2	Collaborative projects in HE (RIA, IA, CSA)	1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	INTERMEDIATE/ADVANCED: SUPP RESEARCHERS: Increase the participation of other R&I actors in FP (universities, research centers; public administration...)	Dependant on government measures regarding COVID-19
ULPGC	Training_1	Introduction to HE	All	BASIC/INTERMEDIATE: SUPP RESEARCHERS: Increase the participation of other R&I actors in FP (universities, research centers; public administration...) + SUPP OR'S OFFICERS TEAMS & EU PROJECT MANAGERS FROM FW PARTNERS: Increase the participation in FP	Dependant on government measures regarding COVID-19
	Trainings_2	Writing successful EU R&I proposals	All, but priority 1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners 3) SMEs (CEO, EU Project Managers) 4) Tecnologos funded by	INTERMEDIATE/ADVANCED: SUPP RESEARCHERS: Increase the participation of other R&I actors in FP (universities, research centers; public administration...) + SUPP OR'S OFFICERS TEAMS & EU PROJECT MANAGERS FROM FW PARTNERS: Increase the participation in FP	Dependant on government measures regarding COVID-19
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_1	ERC: How to design a successful proposal * (if possible)	1) Researchers ULPGC	INTERMEDIATE/ADVANCED: SUPP RESEARCHERS: Increase the participation of other R&I actors in FP (universities, research centers; public administration...)	Dependant on government measures regarding COVID-19
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_2	Management, coordination and implementation of coordinated projects* (if possible)	1) Researchers ULPGC 2) EU Project Manager FCPCT/ULPGC	INTERMEDIATE/ADVANCED: SUPP RESEARCHERS: Increase the participation of other R&I actors in FP (universities, research centers; public administration...) + SUPP OR'S OFFICERS TEAMS & EU PROJECT MANAGERS FROM FW PARTNERS: Increase the participation in FP	Dependant on government measures regarding COVID-19

PLOCAN	Training_1	P o s s i b l	Funding opportunities and proposal preparation for Research Infrastructures and integration on Research Infrastructures networks.	1) SMEs 2) Researchers 3) Technologists/ EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	BASIC/INTERMEDIATE: SUPP RESEARCHERS: Increase the participation of other R&I actors in FP (universities, industry, research centers; public administration...) TEAMS & EU PROJECT MANAGERS FROM FW PARTNERS: Increase the participation in FP	Dependant on government measures regarding COVID-19
	Training_2		[Training/Workshops for clusters and companies] Training 2: Online/face to face workshop organised by FW partner	1) SMEs 2) Researchers 3) Technologists/ EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	BASIC/INTERMEDIATE: SUPP RESEARCHERS: Increase the participation of other R&I actors in FP (universities, industry, research centers; public administration...) TEAMS & EU PROJECT MANAGERS FROM FW PARTNERS: Increase the participation in FP	Dependant on government measures regarding COVID-19
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_1		ERC: How to design a successful proposal - for Horizon Europe* (if possible)	1) Technologist PLOCAN / 2) EU Project Manager PLOCAN	INTERMEDIATE/ADVANCED: SUPP RESEARCHERS: Increase the participation of other R&I actors in FP (universities, research centers; public administration...)	Dependant on government measures regarding COVID-19
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_2		Management, coordination and implementation of coordinated projects -for Horizon Europe* (if possible)	1) Technologist PLOCAN / 2) EU Project Manager PLOCAN	INTERMEDIATE/ADVANCED: SUPP RESEARCHERS: Increase the participation of other R&I actors in FP (universities, research centers; public administration...) + SUPP OR'S OFFICERS TEAMS & EU PROJECT MANAGERS FROM FW PARTNERS: Increase the participation in FP	Dependant on government measures regarding COVID-19
ITC	Training_1		European funding 2021-2027: R&I enterprise projects	1) SMEs (CEO) 2) SMEs (EU Project Managers) 3) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners 4) Technicians / Innovation managers 5) Clusters	BASIC/INTERMEDIATE: SUPP OR'S OFFICERS TEAMS & EU PROJECT MANAGERS FROM FW PARTNERS: Increase the participation in FP; e.g. writing successful R&I proposals; how to find EU opportunities; Introduction to Horizon Europe; Management and coordination of EC-funded projects	Presentially but online if needed due to COVID19 situation
	Trainings_2		Elaboration and management of European projects	1) SMEs (CEO) 2) SMEs (EU Project Managers) 3) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners 4) Technicians / Innovation managers 5) Clusters	BASIC/INTERMEDIATE: SUPP OR'S OFFICERS TEAMS & EU PROJECT MANAGERS FROM FW PARTNERS: Increase the participation in FP; e.g. writing successful R&I proposals; how to find EU opportunities; Introduction to Horizon Europe; Management and coordination of EC-funded projects	Presentially /online
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_1		INFO Day + Training	EU Project Managers	ADVANCED: with experience in FP or EU funds (involved in more than 2-3 EU projects financed)	Presential is preferably
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_2		INFO Day + Training	EU Project Managers	ADVANCED: with experience in FP or EU funds (involved in more than 2-3 EU projects financed)	Presential is preferably
IAC	Training_1		Webinar about the European Research Council (ERC)	All	Trainings/workshops for researchers and technicians on EU Project Management and Project Development	Presentially as possible/Online due to pandemic situation
	Training_2		Technical Management and Economics of HORIZON EUROPE Projects	R&D actors	Trainings/workshops for researchers and technicians on EU Project Management and Project Development	Presentially as possible/Online due to pandemic situation
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_1		TBC			
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_2		TBC			
CE	no budgeted on GA for					

Guadalupe

GUADALUPE - Capacity Training Proposal (WP4-FORWARD project)					
FW Partner	Capacity activity defined by FW GA	Proposed title for the action	Target public	Goal & Skills training	OBSERVATIONS
REG GUA	Training_1	Montage and writing of proposals	Public and private researchers	Increase the competitiveness of proposals focusing on the Excellence, impact and	
	Training_2	Development of european networks for energy domain	Public and private researchers	Increase the capacity to detect and connect to the networks and people active in H2020 (RUP and European partners)	
	Training_3	Development of european networks for SHS domain	Public and private researchers	Increase the capacity to detect and connect to the networks and people active in H2020 (RUP and European partners)	
	Training_4	Development of european networks for agriculture domain			
	Training_5	Development of european networks for health domain	Public and private researchers	Increase the capacity to detect and connect to the networks and people active in H2020 (RUP and European partners)	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_1	Trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	R&D organizations and actor and researchers	Increase the competitiveness of proposals focusing on the Excellence, impact and implementation sections	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_2	Trainings on project management and development	Researchers	Increase the competitiveness of proposals focusing on the Excellence, impact and implementation sections	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_3				
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_4				
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_5	Workshops on proposal co-creation and project implementation	R&I actors	Increase the capacity to detect and connect to the networks and people active in H2020 (RUP and European partners)	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_6				
UA	Training_1	Montage and writing of proposals	R&D organizations and actor and researchers	Increase the competitiveness of proposals focusing on the Excellence, impact and implementation sections	
	Training_2	English Training	R&D organizations and actor and researchers	Increase the capacity to detect and connect to the networks and people active in H2020 (RUP and European partners)	
	Training_3	Technology transfert training	Public and private researchers	Increase the capacity to detect and connect to the networks and people active in H2020 (RUP and European partners)	
	Training_4	Development of european networks for agriculture domain	Public and private researchers	Increase the capacity to detect and connect to the networks and people active in H2020 (RUP and European partners)	
	Training_5	Development of european networks for health domain	Public and private researchers	Increase the capacity to detect and connect to the networks and people active in H2020 (RUP and European partners)	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_1	Workshops on proposal co-creation and project implementation	R&I actors	Increase the capacity to detect and connect to the networks and people active in H2020 (RUP and European partners)	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_2				

Guyana

GUYANA - Capacity Training Proposal (WP4-FORWARD project)					
FW Partner	Capacity activity defined by FW GA	Proposed title for the action	Target public	Goal & Skills training	OBSERVATIONS
CTG (I)	Trainings_1	Training on opportunities H2020	Potential stakeholders or candidates for H2020 financing	Give Information dedicated to H2020 and funding opportunities for French Guiana candidates to foster their participation in HORIZON funding programs	
	Trainings_2	Training action on financing and support for European Projects	Potential candidates for H2020 financing	Give general skills in european projects	
	Trainings_3	Training in productivity and time management	Potential candidates for H2020 financing	Allow to learn organization techniques and prioritizing tasks	
	Trainings_4	Training program in activities and projects management	Potential candidates for H2020 financing	Better planning and management of projects	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_1	Financial Aspects in H2020	Potential candidates for H2020 financing	Give technical and administrative information on how to develop and manage H2020 proposals and projects. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. General aspects of H2020 2. Grant agreement 3. Methods to determine eligible expenses: real costs, unitary, flat-rate, lump-sum 4. ligibility requirements 5. Ineligible expenses 6. Funding percentages 7. Compatibility of European funds 8. Article 8 of the Grant Agreement 9. Article 10 of the Grant Agreement (Best value for money) 10. Types of expenses (direct / indirect) 11. Staff: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 11.1. Hired staff 11.2. In-house consultant 12. Travel 13. Teams <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 13.1. Prototypes and pilot plants 14. Fungibles 15. Third parties 16. Income 17. Indirect costs 18. Internal invoices 19. Financial status 20. Payments 21. Audits 22. Case study 	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_2	Financial Aspects in H2020	Potential candidates for H2020 financing		

CTG (II)	Fellowships to attend training abroad_3	How to design a successful proposal			<p>Give technical and administrative information on how to develop and manage H2020 proposals and projects.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. General aspects of H2020 2. Grant agreement 3. Methods to determine eligible expenses: real costs, unitary, flat-rate, lump-sum 4. Eligibility requirements 5. Ineligible expenses 6. Funding percentages 7. Compatibility of European funds 8. Article 8 of the Grant Agreement 9. Article 10 of the Grant Agreement (Best value for money) 10. Types of expenses (direct / indirect) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 11. Staff: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 11.1. Hired staff 11.2. In-house consultant 12. Travel 13. Teams <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 13.1. Prototypes and pilot plants 14. Fungibles 15. Third parties 16. Income 17. Indirect costs 18. Internal invoices 19. Financial status 20. Payments <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 21. Audits 22. Case study 	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_4					
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_5	Coaching the Project Engineers to support researchers to develop winning research proposals and projects	Participants from support services		<p>Give the support services new competences in terms of coaching researchers in their proposal development effort and a precised methodology to develop winning proposals.</p>	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_6					
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_7					
Fellowships to attend training abroad_8						

UG	Training_1	How to succeed in current European Research programmes	Potential candidates for H2020 financing	Participants gained knowledge on H2020 programme and the future Horizon Europe, along with a methodology based on autodiagnosis allowing participants to identify after each step of the proposal development cycle if the proposal respect the excellence standards of the European Union and if it worth continuing the effort until submission.	
	Training_2	Developing and writing winning grant applications for European research projects	Potential candidates for H2020 financing	Participants gained new knowledge regarding proposal writing requirements and gained methodology and practical tools allowing them to step by step work on the complete project development cycle from conception to submission.	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_1	Coaching the Project Engineers to support researchers to develop winning research proposals and projects	Participants from support services	Give the support services new competences in terms of coaching researchers in their proposal development effort and a precised methodology to develop winning proposals.	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_2	Project management and financial reporting of European Projects	Potential candidates for H2020 financing and Participants from support services	Give skills for planning, budgeting, accounting, financial reporting, internal control, auditing of the project with the aim of managing project resources properly and achieving the project's objectives	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_3		Potential candidates for H2020 financing	Give skills for planning, budgeting, accounting, financial reporting, internal control, auditing of the project with the aim of managing project resources properly and achieving the project's objectives	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_4	Financial Aspects in H2020	Potential candidates for H2020 financing and Participants from support services	<p>information on how to develop and manage the financial part of H2020 proposals and projects.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. General aspects of H2020 2. Grant agreement 3. Methods to determine eligible expenses: real costs, unitary, flat-rate, lump-sum 4. Eligibility requirements 5. Ineligible expenses 6. Funding percentages 7. Compatibility of European funds 8. Article 8 of the Grant Agreement 9. Article 10 of the Grant Agreement (Best value for money) 10. Types of expenses (direct / indirect) 11. Staff: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 11.1. Hired staff 11.2. In-house consultant 12. Travel 13. Teams <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 13.1. Prototypes and pilot plants 14. Fungibles 15. Third parties 16. Income 17. Indirect costs 18. Internal invoices 19. Financial status 20. Payments 21. Audits 22. Case study 	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_5				
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_6	Writing of the Impact Section	Potential candidates for H2020 financing	Better knowledge about proposal writing (impact section)	

GDI	Training_1	Training on Entrepreneurship & Innovation - 1	Researchers and business owners	How to cultivate the mindset and skills of successful entrepreneurs, How to lead innovative teams, How to develop and refine your strategy in today's fast-changing, dynamic markets	
	Training_2	Training on Entrepreneurship & Innovation - 2		Identify opportunities, develop business plans and capture the value created, Learn to collaborate effectively with other actors and specialists internal and external to your company or in specific ecosystems, How to grow your customer base through inbound and outbound marketing	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_1	Exchange Knowledge and cooperation activities	Researchers and business owners	Increase synergies, links and improved transition between the sectors of education, research and business at national and international level	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_2	Exchange Knowledge and cooperation activities		Increase synergies, links and improved transition between the sectors of education, research and business at national and international level	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_3	Knowledge Protection		how to use, protect and monetize your knowledge while working with various partners	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_4				
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_5	Knowledge Transfer		Organize, create, capture or distribute knowledge and ensure its availability for future users	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_6				
SYNERGILE	no budgeted on GA for WP4 activities				

Madeira

MADEIRA - Capacity Training Proposal (WP4-FORWARD project)					
FW Partner	Capacity activity defined by FW GA	Proposed title for the action	Target public	Goal & Skills training	OBSERVATIONS
ARDITTI	Training_1	Funding opportunities in the European Framework Programs for Research &	Makers, Project Managers and R&D organizations in general	Awareness and survey on interest in existing H2020 calls	
	Training_2	Funding opportunities in the European Framework Programs for Research & Innovation (sub event 1)	Researchers, Education and other R&D organizations	Existing H2020 calls / proposal requirements	
	Training_3	Horizon Europe projects proposal co-creation and implementation	R&I actors	FP projects proposal co-creation and project implementation	
	Training_4	Horizon Europe projects management and development	R&I actors	FP projects management and development	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_1	Training on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	Education and other R&D organizations and actors	to market deployment of research results	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_2	Training abroad for researcher in selected TWG	Researchers	skills and research projects proposal development	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_3	Training abroad for researcher in selected TWG	Researchers	skills and research projects proposal development	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_4	Training abroad for researcher in selected TWG	Researchers	skills and research projects proposal development	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_5	Training abroad for researcher in selected TWG	Researchers	skills and research projects proposal development	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_6	Training abroad for researcher in selected TWG	Researchers	skills and research projects proposal development	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_7	Training abroad for researcher in selected TWG	Researchers	skills and research projects proposal development	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_8	Training abroad for researcher in selected TWG	Researchers	skills and research projects proposal development	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_9	Training abroad for researcher in selected TWG	Researchers	skills and research projects proposal development	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_10	Training abroad for researcher in selected TWG	Researchers	skills and research projects proposal development	
UMA	Training_1	Training abroad for researcher in selected TWG	Researchers	skills and research projects proposal development	
	Training_2	Framework Programs for Research & Innovation (sub event 2)	Education and other R&D organizations	Existing H2020 calls / proposal requirements	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_1	Research excellence in Madeira region under the subject of "Smart Islands"	R&I actors	Achieving scientific excellence in research	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_2	Horizon Europe projects proposal co-creation and implementation	R&I actors	FP projects proposal co-creation and project implementation	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_3	Horizon Europe projects management and development	R&I actors	FP projects management and development	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_4	Training abroad for researcher in selected TWG	Researchers	TWG field expertise, networking skills and research projects proposal development	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_5	Training abroad for researcher in selected TWG	Researchers	TWG field expertise, networking skills and research projects proposal development	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_6	Training abroad for researcher in selected TWG	Researchers	TWG field expertise, networking skills and research projects proposal development	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_7	Training abroad for researcher in selected TWG	Researchers	TWG field expertise, networking skills and research projects proposal development	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_8	Training abroad for researcher in selected TWG	Researchers	TWG field expertise, networking skills and research projects proposal development	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_9	Training abroad for researcher in selected TWG	Researchers	TWG field expertise, networking skills and research projects proposal development	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_10	Training abroad for researcher in selected TWG	Researchers	skills and research projects proposal development	

Martinique

MARTINIQUE - Capacity Training Proposal (WP4-FORWARD project)					
FW Partner	Capacity activity defined by FW GA	Proposed title for the action	Target public	Goal & Skills training	OBSERVATIONS
CTM	Training_1	How to respond to a H2020 or HORIZON Europe call for projects		Design a project that meets the requirements of the European Commission	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_1	CIRAD	researchers	Write a successful technical proposal	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_2	Technopole CACEM	Company	Understand the rules of participation, the H2020 and Horizon Europe procedures to better support Martinican companies	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_3	IFREMER	researchers	Know the funding opportunities of the H2020 & Horizon Europe program	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_4	GREEN TECHNOLOGIE	Company	Learn to build an R & D & I financing file	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_5	L3MA/Pôle University	researchers	Understand the rules of participation, the H2020 and Horizon Europe procedures	

Mayote

MAYOTE - Capacity Training Proposal (WP4-FORWARD project)					
FW Partner	Capacity activity defined by FW GA	Proposed title for the action	Target public	Goal & Skills training	OBSERVATIONS
CDM	Training_1	Atelier sur le management et développement de projets de recherche	Researchers	Increase the competitiveness of proposals with a focus on the specific added value	
	Training_2	Atelier sur la co-création et mise en œuvre de projets de recherche	R&I actors (both public & private)	Increase the capacity to lead projects and proposals on R&I	

Reunion

REUNION - Capacity Training Proposal (WP4-FORWARD project)					
FW Partner	Capacity activity defined by FW GA	Proposed title for the action	Target public	Goal & Skills training	OBSERVATIONS
NEXA	Training_1	Sensibilisation à la RRI (Recherche et Innovation Responsable)	Researchers	Increase the awareness on RRI / Integrate RRI principles in their practices	
	Training_2	Aperçu des opportunités de financement pour les SHS	HSS researchers	Increase the willingness of social scientists to participate in H Europe	
	Training_3	Montage et rédaction de proposals	Public & Private researchers	Increase the competitiveness of proposals focusing on the Excellence, impact and implementation sections	
	Training_4	Développement de réseaux européens en SHS	HSS researchers	Increase the capacity to detect and connect to the networks and people active in H2020 (HSS session)	
	Training_5	Développement de réseaux européens en Energy	Energy Researchers and entrepreneurs	Increase the capacity to detect and connect to the networks and people active in H2020 (Energy session)	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_1	2 common training sessions will be organized in BXL focusing on networking capacities and EU policies to allow researchers to join	Session 1 will be dedicated to HSS researchers, Session 2 will be dedicated to Energy Researchers & entrepreneurs	Understanding EU policies in R&I, how to connect to the most dynamic EU players	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_2				
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_3				
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_4				
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_5				
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_6				
UR	Training_1	ANR TOUR	Researchers and entrepreneurs	Increase the competitiveness of proposals	
	Training_2	Développement de réseaux européens en Biodiversité & Santé	Biodiversity & Health Researchers and entrepreneurs	Capacity building for networking and connectivity with EU clusters	
	Training_3	Médiation scientifique	Researchers	Increase the impact of communication and networking	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_1	2 common training sessions organized with NEXA	Session 1 will be dedicated to HSS researchers, Session 2 will be dedicated to Energy Researchers & entrepreneurs	Understanding EU policies in R&I, how to connect to the most dynamic EU players	
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_2				
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_3				
	Fellowships to attend training abroad_4				

Saint Martin

Saint Martin - Capacity Training Proposal (WP4-FORWARD project)						
FW Partner	Capacity activity defined by FW GA		Proposed title for the action	Target public	Goal & Skills training	OBSERVATIONS
COMSM	Training_1	P r o	Introduction to EU FUNDING	Stakeholders, general public	Understanding the EU levers in funds	
	Training_2		H2020 an opportunity of innovation growth	Stakeholders, public officers,	RIS 3 innovation policies for 21-27	
CCISM	no budged on GA for WP4 activities					

ANNEX 3: Final Regional Plan Proposal per Region on WP4 activities

Annex 3 is the annex used to compile the final Regional Capacity Plan Proposal, as soon as the events are confirmed to take place. In this table all events are contemplated, funded by FORWARD budgeted or not, as long as it's aligned with FORWARD goals in WP4. It is one table per each partner region, to be managed by the WP4 leader in coordination with the Regional Coordinator for WP4 from each OR in the project.

One per region							
REGION:							
REGIONAL COORDINATOR:							
FORWARD partner	Type of capacity action	Task	In the context of the GA (Yes/No)	Time frame for execution	Name/title of the Capacity action	Goal & Skills training	Target public

ANNEX 4: Actions and follow up report template

This annex is a word file where each FW partner will report on the implementation of their activities, foreseen in Task 4.2 and Task 4.4, that were filled in the previous annexes, in order to describe in more detail the activities, methodology, participants profile, etc.

FORWARD WP4 Capacity and training activities **Actions and follow up report template** **(Task 4.2; Task 4.4)**

Event organiser [Institution]

Type of event: (training; workshop; twining..)

Name of the event:

Introduction

(2 to 3 paragraphs)

Technical reporting:

Executive summary

(2 to 4 paragraphs)

Objectives of the event

(Skills to gain and target public – number and field of work)

Date and location (venue).

Contents

Summarise the programme

(resumed version)

Communication

Summarize and document all advertising and media tools used (with links and annexes if possible)

Date	Media	Impact achieved

Agents of the event

Trainer/Speakers (short CV info)

Participants, type and number of participants

Results:

Achievement of objectives:

General conclusions (link the skills gained with a need expressed in previous consultations in FW project – namely in WP2)

Annexes:

Photos

(at least 4: with the group, the trainer, group photo – showing the FORWARD logo preferably)

Financial reporting:

Table of budget of the event compared to final actual costs.

Type of cost	Entity/Name	Budgeted cost	Actual cost	Comments
Venue renting				
Trainer/Speakers fee (in €)				
Other expenses (material; catering, etc)				

The budget available for this event was [] €, the final cost of the event has been [] €.

ANNEX 5: POWER POINT from the WP4 Workshop in Reunion Island, July 2019

These are the power point slides presented to the several FORWARD partners present in this event that resulted in a overall vision from the WP2 diagnose and vision over their region regarding the several steps of analysis of each region need in terms of capacity and training needs in each OR, in the context of the FORWARD WP4 goals.

The following first three slides are general and introductory of the following slides, with the inputs by OR. This individual information, by OR, is the source of the information provided in figure 4. to figure 7., a resumed and global vision, referenced in the methodology paragraph for WP4 (from page 14 on).

Forward – Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions
WP 4
Capacity building and training activities

Workshop
Co-creation of a Capacity Plan for OR's R&I ecosystem
By region
July 2019, Saint Denis, Reunion

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824550.

WP4 CO-CREATION BUILDING PROCESS

WP4 CO-CREATION BUILDING PROCESS

Workshop Inputs by OR

Azores

STEP 1 EVALUATING CAPACITIES (SELF-EVALUATION) -Azores

STRENGTH

- 1. Attractivity/ differentiated potential (expl. geothermic; space; biodiversity; volcanology) -Geo-strategic position with natural advantages and adaptation /resilience abilities
- 2. Experience in networks as ERA /H2020/ Instruments for SME's
- 3. Young, small, well connected, resheable research community

WEAKNESS

- 1. Lack of coordination/leadership of FP projects (self-confidence)
- 2. Weak performance of the R&I ecosystem in FP programs due to the lack of regional support services (awareness actions; orientation; validation; support)
- 3. Capabilities of analysis and write proposals for calls

Name 3 in your region, by priority

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019710

STEP 2 Main **priorities** for capacity in Azores's R&I ecosystem

What we (don't) have (present reality) → TO → What we need to have (future)

- Improve rate of proposals submitted and approved in FP
- Poor alignment between researchers and business sector TO stronger connections/collaboration/synergies/knowledge
- From lack of confidence and knowledge on calls to develop leadership skills and better knowledge on FP projects

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019710

Canary Islands

STEP 1 **EVALUATING CAPACITIES (SELF-EVALUATION) –Canary Islands**

STRENGTH

- 1. Research infrastructures & research excellence (aquaculture;marine-maritime; astrophysics)
- 2. Experience in ERA Chains/H2020/SME Instruments (visibility of H2020 among companies)
- 3. Existence of supporting offices
- 4. National funding & Support to representation of H2020

WEAKNESS

- 1. Weak self-assessment evaluation of researchers
- 2. Lack of skills in analysis of calls of proposal/ proposal writing
- 3. Strategic/multidisciplinary networking skills
- 4. Low level of collaboration among research organizations/knowledge & experience transfer

Name 3 in your region, by priority

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

STEP 2

Main **priorities for capacity in Canary's R&I ecosystem**

What we (don't) have (present reality) → TO → What we need to have (future)

- Good success rate **TO** higher number of winning proposals submitted
- Poor alignment of researchers with business sector **TO** stronger connections/collaboration with industry/SME'S
- Low openness of researchers & research groups (multidisciplinary;SME's; International level) **TO** change of mentality //Opportunity for multidisciplinary/multi-actors collaboration and specific skills building activities

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

Guadalupe

STEP 1 EVALUATING CAPACITIES (SELF-EVALUATION) -GUADALUPE

STRENGTH

- Knowledge and use of expert network
- Attractivity potential (geothermy)
- Multidisciplinary of research capacity

WEAKNESS

- Financial resources and capacity to organize
- Weak culture of innovation
- Lack of communication: dissemination of research results
- Lack of scientific skills of the territory
- Lack of financial tools
- Lack of lobbying

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 621620

Name 3 in your region, by priority

STEP 2 Main priorities for capacity in Guadalupe's R&I ecosystem

What we (don't) have (present reality) → What we need to have (future)

- Political in charge of innovation – better understand of what is innovation from technology
- Team to assist research team and SME to access and understand H2020 calls: develop skills on team or create regional contact point
- Capacity to manage local network – go to international scale

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 621620

Select 3 in your region – use your table

STEP 3 Lacks on excellence knowlege transfer in Guadalupe

SOURCE

Expl:
Universities/
Researchers

Name 3 solutions to fill in the gap

- In between people - network
- Promote training to co-design and co-implemente with stakeholders .
Increase the uptake of research results
- Mapping the research capabilities, the way to access infrastructures

END USER

Policy making/
Market/
companies

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 621620

CO-CREATION DIMENSION CAPACITY BUILDING:

a. Structural – needs (base)

- Practice english
- Manage innovative projects
- Dissemination of reasearch results
- Engaging stakeholders
- Culture of H2020 programs
- Networking

b. Transversal – skills (specific)

- Budged and find calls on H2020 programs
- Manangind and policies for programs
- Trainings on H2020

Based on the previews 4 steps:
 Identified 3 typologies of trainings and capacity activities addressing this two points **Guadalupe**

Logos: Governo dos Açores, FRCT, forward, and EU.

French Guyane

STEP 1

EVALUATING CAPACITIES (SELF-EVALUATION) - FRENCH GUYANE

STRENGTH

- 3. Multidisciplinarity of research capacities
- 1. Knowledge and use of expert network
- 2. Potential of specific attractiveness (Spatial; geothermy)

WEAKNESS

- 1. Financial resources and capacity to organize
- 2. Weak culture of innovation
- 3. Insufficient external communication: scientific skills of the territory; financial tools; lobbying

Name 3 in your region, by priority

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821510.

STEP 2

Main **priorities** for capacity in FRENCH GUYANE R&I ecosystem

What we (don't) have (present reality) **TO** What we need to have (future)

- Sensibilize awareness of the culture of innovation
- Financial engineering adapted to small business
- Capacity of answers to H2020 calls for projects

*Select 3 in your region – use your table

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821510.

STEP 3

Lacks on **excellence knowledge transfer** in FRENCH GUYANE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821510.

In yellow the inclusions by the representatives of Guyane

CO-CREATION DIMENSION

CAPACITY BUILDING:

a. Structural – needs (base)

- _____
- _____
- _____

b. Transversal – skills (specific)

- _____
- _____
- _____

TO BE COMPLETED

Based on the previews 4 steps:
Identified 3 typologies of trainings and capacity activities addressing this two points in **Guyane**

Logos: Governo dos Açores, FRCT, forward, and a small EU logo with text: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150."

Madeira

STEP 1 EVALUATING CAPACITIES (SELF-EVALUATION) -Madeira

STRENGTH

- 1. Adequate project management/administrative support
- 2. Young, small, well connected, reachable research community
- 3. Known-how on H2020 training capabilities (not on full capacity)

WEAKNESS

- 3. Lack of coordination/leadership of FP projects (self-confidence)
- 2. Lack of collaborative skills/networking
- 1. Lack of political awareness and social recognition of R&I activities

Name 3 in your region, by priority

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101015001.

STEP 2 Main priorities for capacity in Madeira's R&I ecosystem

What we (don't) have (present reality) → TO → What we need to have (future)

- From having training courses to more regular/customized sessions
- Science at the market (outreach/dissemination of R&DI) to amplify number of days
- Need to develop leadership trainings and promote courses on emotional intelligence...

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101015001.

STEP 3 Lacks on excellence knowledge transfer in Madeira

SOURCE

Expl: Universities/Research/ Researchers

Name 3 solutions to fill in the gap

- Outreach – General public
- SME- Innovation platform – EC call for proposals
- Dynamic RIS3/S3 (quadruple hélix) at the level of academia; state; industry; civil-society

END USER

Policy making/ Market/ General public

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101015001.

CO-CREATION DIMENSION

CAPACITY BUILDING:

a. Structural – needs (base)

- Knowledge of EU/CE framework structure and network
- Innovation platform (to bridge knowledge transport)
- _____

b. Transversal – skills (specific)

- Implement the training courses indicated in the STEPS (in particular 1 and 2)
- _____
- _____

Based on the previews 4 steps:
Identified 3 typologies of trainings and capacity activities addressing this two points in **Madeira**

TO BE COMPLETED

Logos: Governo dos Açores, FRCT, forward, EU

Martinique

STEP 1

EVALUATING CAPACITIES (SELF-EVALUATION) IN MARTINIQUE

STRENGTH

- 3.Existence of little stars
- 1.Strategic geographical position & natural assets & adptation capacities

WEAKNESS

- 4.Lack of connection to H2020 champions (network)
- 3.Low performing of the R&I ecosystem + lack of support services
- 2.Local policies do not act as levers to enter H2020
- 1.Lack of understanding of H2020 and it's importance to development R&I political and individual level

Name 3 in your region, by priority

Logos: forward, EU

STEP 2 Main **priorities** for **capacity** in Martinique's R&I ecosystem

What we (don't) have (present reality) → What we need to have (future)

- Inexistence of Support services (H2020) to develop the existing ecosystem. Technicopole: 1. build/construct practical training on H2020 (How to write proposals; budget; create network); 2. Build a specific practical training dedicated to H2020 projects – Support services

*Select 3 in your region – use your table

STEP 3 Lacks on **excellence knowledge transfer** in Martinique

STEP 4 **Financing flow** in Martinique

CO-CREATION DIMENSION

CAPACITY BUILDING:

a. Structural – needs (base)

- Develop and structure existent potential to create/develop the R&I ecosystem
- Create actions for joint creation of action plan
- Create events to foster collaboration between local researchers and "champions"
- Evens for local awareness
- Promote conexions with EU network

b. Transversal – skills (specific)

- Specific training on R&I and H2020/Horizont Europe: find/identify calls; submit projects (write excelente impact sections) and manage projects
- Specific Support service dedicated to Horizont budge: valorization of Support services; write excelente impact/sectorial

Based on the previews 4 steps:
Identified 3 typologies of trainings and capacity activities addressing this two points **in Martinique**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019749.

Mayote

STEP 1

EVALUATING CAPACITIES (SELF-EVALUATION) –Mayotte

STRENGTH

- Mayotte is a real hotspot in biodiversity
- Source of research (lagoon for aquaculture & marine activities, endemic plants for agriculture, vulcanology, geological activities)
- Economic growth of the territory
- Research-friendly national regulations
- Existence of supporting offices
- Strategic geographical position
- National funding & Support to ESFI

WEAKNESS

- Lack of research infrastructures & research excellence
- Lack of connection with H2020 actors
- Lack of information on calls of proposal/ proposal writing
- Lack of strategic/multidisciplinary networking skills
- Low level of collaboration among research organizations/knowledge & experience transfer
- Lack of experience in H2020/SME Instruments (visibility of H2020 among companies)
- Lack of promotion of H2020

Name 3 in your region, by priority

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019749.

STEP 2

Main **priorities** for capacity in Mayotte's R&I ecosystem

What we (don't) have (present reality) **TO** What we need to have (future)

- Lack of research centers **TO** Several research centers and labs,
- No doctorant programmes **TO** Several doctorant programme in strategic fields (marine, agriculture, geothermal, circular economy...
- Lack of trust and confidence from local banks on fundamental researchers **TO** Strong cooperation between local banks and researchers
- Lack of proposals in H2020 **TO** more information on call propals
- Technical Assistance **TO** More participation
- Participation **TO** good rate of success of winning proposals submitted
- Very poor alignment of researchers with business sector **TO** stronger connections/collaboration with industry/SME'S, event to reach the triple helix
- Low ability in building innovation strategy and management **TO** Strong innovative structures

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

STEP 3

Lacks on **excellence knowledge transfer** in Mayotte

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

STEP 4

Financing flow in Mayotte

STAGES

Identify what are the stages for **financing captation** of the all life of the project: from presentation to managing the project

1*(Identify all the interested calls, identify the local stakeholders). **Objective** will be to raise awareness and give information on EU financing opportunities.

2*(participation as workpackage responsible). Strategy: in LGT become a project leader

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019150.

CO-CREATION DIMENSION CAPACITY BUILDING:

a. Structural – needs (base)

- Better connection with end-user of research innovation research topics, collaboration projects)
- More (quality) proposal submitted
- Entering more proposals as partners (connections with “champions”)

b. Transversal – skills (specific)

- Design-Thinking (for definition of research topics; collaborative projects)
- Researchers: Self-assessment; Self-confidence
- Presentation/communication – to propose your group as partner for instance)
- Proposal writing (including budgeted) with success cases for Regions

Based on the previews 4 steps:
 Identified 3 typologies of trainings and capacity activities addressing this two points in Mayote

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019100

Reunion

STEP 1 EVALUATING CAPACITIES (SELF-EVALUATION) - REUNION

<p> STRENGTH</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> 3.Existence of little stars <input type="checkbox"/> 1.Strategic geographical position & natural assets & adptation capacities <input type="checkbox"/> 2.Research thematic of the future (are of even more importance to OR's) <input type="checkbox"/> 4. Support services (Reunion) open to all actors of the territory 	<p> WEAKNESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> 4.Lack of connection to H2020 champions (network) <input type="checkbox"/> 3.Low performing of the R&I ecosystem + lack of support services <input type="checkbox"/> 2.Local policies do not act as levers to enter H2020 <input type="checkbox"/> 1.Lack of understanding of H2020 and it's importance to development R&I political and individual level
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019100

Name 3 in your region, by priority

STEP 2 Main **priorities** for capacity in Reunion R&I ecosystem

What we (don't) have (present reality) → What we need to have (future)

- 1. Increase capacity to write excelente impact actions (training);
- 3. Create action plan to increase collaboration between "locals" researchers with national and international "project champions";
- 2. Identify the champions by thematics

Select 3 in your region – use your table

STEP 3 Lacks on **excellence knowlege transfer** in Reunion

Name 3 solutions to fill in the gap

SOURCE → END USER

Expl: Universities → Policy making/ Market

- Valorization of support services: financed by public authorities and private entities- impact public policies and business solutions
- Increase local knowlage transfer by ensuring selection criteria: encourage and dissemination of local research and research uptake
- Matching researcher and private sector

SETP 4 Financing flow in Reunion

STAGES

SOURCE → End-user/ Market

EU → OR's

EU office for OR's – lobby support → Awareness & training: local awareness & specific H2020 training → Connection to EU network: 1. Identify the networks of interest; 2. Organize events for researchers network → Proposal writing & submission: consultant to help with the construction of the project → Project follow-up → End-user/ Market

Identify what are the stages for **financing captation** of the all life of the project: from presentation to managing the project

CO-CREATION DIMENSION

CAPACITY BUILDING:

a. Structural – needs (base)

- Develop and structure existant potential to create/develop the R&I ecosystem
- Create actions for joint creation of action plan
- Create events to foster collaboration between local researchers and "champions"
- Evens for local awareness
- Promote conections with EU network

b. Transversal – skills (specific)

- Specific training on R&I and H2020/Horizont Europe: find/identify calls; submit projects (write excelente impact sections) and manage projects
- Specific Support service dedicated to Horizont budge: valorization of Support services; write excelente impact/sectorial

Based on the previews 4 steps:
Identified 3 typologies of trainings and capacity activities addressing this two points in Reunion

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Governo dos Açores

Saint Martin

STEP 1

EVALUATING CAPACITIES (SELF-EVALUATION) - Saint Martin

STRENGTH

- 3. Existence of little stars
- 1. Strategic geographical position & natural assets & adptation capacities
- 2. Research thematic of the future (are of even more importance to OR's)
- 4. Support services (Reunion) open to all actors of the territory

WEAKNESS

- 4. Lack of connection to H2020 champions (network)
- 3. Low performing of the R&I ecosystem + lack of support services
- 2. Local policies do not act as levers to enter H2020
- 1. Lack of understanding of H2020 and it's importance to development R&I political and individual level

Name 3 in your region, by priority

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STEP 2 Main **priorities** for capacity in Saint Martin R&I ecosystem

What we (don't) have (present reality) → What we need to have (future)

- ❑ The need to develop/structure existant actors to create the R&I ecosystem – build specific training on R&I and H2020 programs

Select 3 in your region – use your table

Logos: European Union, Governo dos Açores, FRCT, forward

STEP 3 Lacks on **excellence knowlege** transfer in Saint Martin

NAME 3 solutions to fill in the gap

SOURCE: Expl: Universities

END USER: Policy making/ Market

- ❑ Valorization of support services: financed by public authorities and private entities- impact public policies and business solutions
- ❑ Increase local knowlege transfer by ensuring selection criteria: encourage and dissemination of local research and research uptake
- ❑ Matching researcher and private sector

Logos: European Union, Governo dos Açores, FRCT, forward

SETP 4 Financing flow in Saint Martin

STAGES

SOURCE: EU

End-user/ Market OR's

- Awareness & training: local awareness & specific H2020 training
- Connection to EU network:
 1. Identify the networks of interest:
 2. Organize events for researchers network
- Proposal writing & submission: consultant to help with the construction of the project
- Project follow-up

Identify what are the stages for **financing captation** of the all life of the project: from presentation to managing the project

Logos: European Union, Governo dos Açores, FRCT, forward

CO-CREATION DIMENSION

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Based on the previews 4 steps:

Identified 3 typologies of trainings and capacity activities addressing this two points **Saint Martin**

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